

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

MASTER OF LAND VALUATION AND MANAGEMENT

JUAN V. SARMIENTO JR.

**AN ALTERNATIVE ENTRY AND EXIT ROUTE'S INFLUENCE ON LAND PRICES:
A CASE STUDY**

Thesis Adviser:

ASST. PROF. CESAR Z. LUNA
Faculty of Management and Development Studies

3 April 2024

Permission is given for the following people to have access to this thesis, subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy and any contractual obligations:

Invention (I)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes or <input type="checkbox"/> No
Publication (P)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes or <input type="checkbox"/> No
Confidential (C)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes or <input type="checkbox"/> No
Free (F)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes or <input type="checkbox"/> No

Student's signature: *Juan V. Sarmiento Jr.*

Thesis adviser signature: *Cesar Z. Luna*

University Permission Page

AN ALTERNATIVE ENTRY AND EXIT ROUTE'S INFLUENCE ON LAND PRICES: A CASE STUDY

"I hereby grant the University of the Philippines, a non-exclusive, worldwide, royalty-free license to reproduce, publish and publicly distribute copies of this academic work in whatever form subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy and any contractual obligations, as well as more specific permission marking on the title page.

"Specifically, I grant the following rights to the University:

- a. Upload a copy of the work in the theses database of the college/school/institute/department and in any other databases available on the public internet;*
- b. Publish the work in the college/school/institute/department journal, both in print and electronic or digital format and online; and*
- c. Give open access to the work, thus allowing "fair use" of the work in accordance with the provision of the Intellectual Property Code of the Philippines (Republic Act No. 8293), especially for teaching, scholarly and research purposes."*

Juan V. Sarmiento Jr.

Juan V. Sarmiento Jr. and 3 April 2024
Signature over Student Name and Date

Acceptance Page

This Thesis of **JUAN V. SARMIENTO JR.**, titled “**AN ALTERNATIVE ENTRY AND EXIT ROUTE’S INFLUENCE ON LAND PRICES: A CASE STUDY**,” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, UP Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree **Master of Land Valuation and Management**.

ASST. PROF. CESAR Z. LUNA
Chair, Advisory Committee

31 March 2025

Date

ATTY. PAUL HEHERSON M. BALITE
Member, Advisory Committee

03 April 2025

Date

DR. FERDINAND C. MAQUITO
Member, Advisory Committee

29 April 2025

Date

FINAFLOR F. TAYLAN, DProfSt
Dean
Faculty of Management and Development Studies

April 30, 2025

(Date)

Biographical Sketch

Juan V. Sarmiento Jr. has a B.S. Statistics degree from the University of the Philippines Diliman (1980), a diploma in Land Valuation and Management (with distinction) from the UP Open University (2014) and a master's degree in Land Valuation and Management from UPOU (2024). He is a real estate appraiser who made it to the Top 10 in the 2015 licensure exams and is also a licensed real estate broker.

An award-winning reporter, he subsequently became a senior desk editor of the Philippine Daily Inquirer, where he worked for 30 years. He also edited the newspaper's weekly "Talk of the Town" special section.

Among his awards are the grand prize in the Pan Asia Journalism Award for Excellence in Business Reporting sponsored by Citibank and a citation from the Society of Publishers in Asia for editorial excellence.

He is an associate editor of the digital magazine CoverStory.ph, part of whose mission is to deliver insightful and relevant articles that address the needs of its audiences.

Acknowledgment

Thanks to Pleasant Village Homeowners Association president Danny Garcia for a detailed background of the City Alternative Route Entry and Exit System. Also, to residents Ludy Huiso, Jason Aquino, Perseus Calvario and James Ledesma, as well as former HOA president Danny Carandang and personnel Riza Roxas, Joseph Villalon, Erwin Dellosa and Christian Ala. Huiso was particularly helpful in providing information about the subdivision's origins. Others who gave information about the new road included residents of neighboring subdivisions (Romeo Bautista, Marijo Inserto, Charing Daza and Malou Escuadro) and developer Niño Barrion. Councilor Raul Corro recalled the initial negotiations with Filinvest Alabang Inc. and opening of the road to traffic. Without the assent of Acting Assessor Genalyn Estrera and coordination with Francis Muñoz I could not have obtained prices of land sold in Pleasant that were manually collected from deeds of absolute sale kept in the Assessor's Office. Rosemarie Geli, acting head of Community Affairs and Development Office, and Camille Joyce Ramos were accommodating in providing information that I requested from the office. Also, thanks to Danidon Nolasco, Chito Valerio, Allan Balila, Tez Valencia, Pitz Adriano, internal revenue officer Ignacio Camba Jr. and appraiser Lambert Modina. The suggestions of the thesis panel committee, headed by Land Valuation and Management Program Chair Cesar Luna, with Atty. Paul Heherson Balite (who gave his comments a few semesters ago) and Max Maquito, Ph.D., as members, helped improve my report. So, thank you. Finally, my thanks to Juan Paolo L. Sarmiento for assisting me in measuring the length and width of the CARES sections in Pleasant and for serving as my IT support.

Dedication

To Menchie, Mayi, Pao and Ana

Abstract

Land prices in a residential subdivision soared after an access road to a central business district (CBD) in southern Metro Manila opened initially in early 2013 and for good in December 2014, improving the subdivision's accessibility. The CBD in Muntinlupa City happens to host not only an interchange of a toll expressway and ramps of an elevated toll road, but also passenger transport terminals. Before the City Alternative Route Entry and Exit System came into service the subdivision could be reached only via an often-congested national road. Sales data show that access and proximity to the alternative route boosted property values in the subdivision, as it saw bigger price increases than those in a community with no access to the new road network.

Keywords: Influence on Land Prices; Accessibility; Traffic Congestion; Alternative Route; Central Business District

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title Page	i
University Permission Page	ii
Acceptance Page	iii
Biographical Sketch	iv
Acknowledgment	v
Dedication	vi
Abstract	vii
Table of Contents	viii
List of Tables	x
List of Figures	xi
List of Acronyms	xi
CHAPTER I: THE RESEARCH PROBLEM	
Background of the Study	1
Statement of the Problem	3
Objectives of the Study	4
Significance	5
Scope and Limitation	5
CHAPTER II: THEORETICAL BACKGROUND	
Review of Literature	10
Proximity	10
Paved Streets	12
Catchment Area	12
Quality of Service	13
Negative Externalities	14
Accessibility	15
Middle Class	15
Theoretical Framework	16
CHAPTER III: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	
Research Design	18
Case Study	18
Difference in Differences	19
Sampling Technique	20
Assessor's Office	20

Test and Control Groups	21
Software, Manual Retrieval	22
Rounds of Sampling	22
Prices from Agents	23
CHAPTER IV: RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS	
BIR and CARES	26
Price Surge	28
Sales Data	28
Pandemic	29
Deeds of Absolute Sale	33
Price Increase Due to the New Road	35
Capitalization	40
Project Cost	41
Construction	42
Replacement Cost New	42
Right of Way	43
Donation	44
Short on Amenities	50
Alternative Route	52
Faster Commute	53
Expressway and Skyway	55
Sole Entry and Exit Point	56
Directive from the President	57
Caring for One Another	58
Long Road to Cares	59
Rejection	59
Mayor Takes Action	60
Unpublished IRR and Suit	61
Pressing for Reopening	62
MOA, Access Road Reopens	63
Rise of CBD	64
Controversial Bidding	65
Filinvest City	66
CHAPTER V: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS	
Conclusion	68
Influence on Land Value	68
Generalization to Theoretical Propositions	69
Recommendations	70
Land-Value Capture	70
RPT, Building Capacity	70
Levies	71
Valuation Tool Kit	72
REFERENCES	73

APPENDICES

APPENDIX A	
Guards as Real Estate Agents	78
APPENDIX B	
Near Workplace, Rental Business	80
APPENDIX C	
Land Transactions in Three Subdivisions: 2009-2021	84
APPENDIX D	
Sampling Rounds in Pleasant, Greenheights and Lakeview	98

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Price of Lots in Pleasant from 2013 to 2021	30
Table 2: Percentage Change in Prices in Pleasant in 2013-2016, 2013-2019 and 2013-2021	31
Table 3: Average Prices in Pleasant, Greenheights and Lakeview in 2010, 2016 and 2019	34
Table 4: Percentage Change in Prices in Pleasant, Greenheights and Lakeview in 2010-2016, 2016-2019	35
Table 5: Pleasant and Lakeview Prices in 2010 and 2016, Excluding Outliers and Multiple Transactions	36
Table 6: Pleasant and Lakeview Prices in 2010 and 2016, Including Outliers and Sale of Multiple Lots	36
Table 7: Pleasant and Lakeview Prices in 2010 and 2019, Excluding an Outlier	37
Table 8: Pleasant and Lakeview Prices in 2010 and 2019, Including an Outlier in Lakeview	37
Table 9: Greenheights and Lakeview Prices in 2010 and 2016, Excluding an Outlier	37
Table 10: Greenheights and Lakeview Prices in 2010 and 2016, Including an Outlier in Lakeview	38
Table 11: Greenheights and Lakeview Prices in 2016 and 2019, Excluding Outliers	38
Table 12: Greenheights and Lakeview Prices in 2016 and 2019, Including Outliers in Lakeview in 2016 and Greenheights in 2019	38
Table 13: Greenheights and Lakeview 2010 and 2019 Prices, Excluding an Outlier in Lakeview in 2010 and Greenheights in 2019	39
Table 14: Greenheights and Lakeview Prices in 2010 and 2019, Including Outliers	39
Table 15: Pleasant Prices in 2010	45
Table 16: Pleasant Prices in 2016, Excluding Outliers and Sale of Multiple Lots	45
Table 17: Pleasant Prices in 2016, Including Outliers and Sale of Multiple Lots	45
Table 18: Pleasant Prices in 2019	46
Table 19: Greenheights Prices in 2010	46
Table 20: Greenheights Prices in 2016	46
Table 21: Greenheights Prices in 2019, Excluding Outliers and Sale of Multiple Lots	47

Table 22: Greenheights Prices in 2019, Including Outliers and Sale of Multiple Lots	47
Table 23: Lakeview Prices in 2010, Excluding an Outlier and Sale of Multiple Lots	48
Table 24: Lakeview Prices in 2010, Including an Outlier	48
Table 25: Lakeview Prices in 2016, Excluding an Outlier	49
Table 26: Lakeview Prices in 2016, Including an Outlier	49
Table 27: Lakeview Prices in 2019	49

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 Muntinlupa and other cities of Metro Manila	7
Figure 2 Central Business District of Muntinlupa at sunrise	8
Figure 3. SLEx and Filinvest City interchange	8
Figure 4. Pleasant and environs	9
Figure 5. CARES and nearby subdivisions	24
Figure 6. Zonal values in Pleasant and Lakeview: 2007-2016	27
Figure 7. Prices of lots in Pleasant from 2013 to 2021	31
Figure 8. Access road in Pleasant from Filinvest City	32
Figure 9. Entrance to Filinvest City from Pleasant	32
Figure 10. Corporate Avenue	33
Figure 11. Average prices in Pleasant, Greenheights and Lakeview: 2010, 2016 and 2019	34
Figure 12. Lot plan of Pleasant	41
Figure 13. Covered court	51
Figure 14. Part of Mandarin Ave. with no improvements until 2021	51
Figure 15. Vicinity map of CARES	52
Figure 16. CARES traffic sign	53
Figure 17. Filinvest sticker for 2023 issued to a car owner	55
Figure 18: Campaign poster of Councilor Raul Corro	58
Figure 19: Barangay road between Camella 2 and Camella 2D	63

LIST OF ACRONYMS

BIR	Bureau of Internal Revenue
BPO	Business Process Outsourcing
CBD	Central Business District
DOAS	Deed of Absolute Sale
DPWH	Department of Public Works and Highways
FAI	Filinvest Alabang Inc.
FEU	Far Eastern University
HOA	Homeowners Association
IRR	Implementing Rules and Regulations
LEED	Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design

MOA	Memorandum of Agreement
MRT 3	Metro Rail Transit 3
NBP	New Bilibid Prison
PEA	Public Estates Authority
PVHOA	Pleasant Village Homeowners Association
RCN	Replacement Cost New
RITM	Research Institute for Tropical Medicine
RPT	Real Property Tax
RTC	Regional Trial Court
SHDA	Subdivision and Housing Developers Association
SLEx	South Luzon Expressway
SMCPR	Soldiers, Mutual, Camella, Pleasant and RCE
SMV	Schedule of Market Values
SVL	Serum and Vaccine Laboratory

Chapter I

THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

Background of the Study

Pleasant Village (Pleasant) is one of the subdivisions that sprang up in Muntinlupa not long after South Luzon Expressway (SLEX) was built. SLEX, a 12-kilometer toll road between Nichols and Alabang, opened to traffic in 1970, cutting travel time to Muntinlupa from Manila, and from Pasay, Makati, Mandaluyong and Quezon City – all contiguous to a capital that had long been bursting at the seams.

Muntinlupa was then a town better known for the New Bilibid Prison, the national penitentiary. Besides Pleasant, among the residential subdivisions that sprouted in Muntinlupa due to the faster travel time was the 661-hectare upscale Ayala Alabang Village, a former mango plantation of the Madrigals that became in just a few years a local government unto itself (Ayala Alabang Village Association, 2019). Others included Alabang Hills, Soldiers Hills Village, Mutual Homes, South Greenheights, Susana Heights, Camella Homes and later Katarungan Village.

Muntinlupa became a highly urbanized first-class city in 1995. By 2000 most of Metro Manila had been built-up, so that practically all the new spatial growth over a 10-year period since then had taken place in nearby provinces (World Bank, 2015). Subdivisions have been rising in Cavite and Laguna – provinces adjacent to Muntinlupa – and even farther south in Batangas, where land prices are more affordable than those in the metropolis.

As a result, sections of Cavite, Laguna and Batangas provinces – all linked to Muntinlupa and the capital by SLEX – have become part of the urban agglomeration of Manila, or the Manila urban area, based on built-up footprint (Deuskar & Zhang, 2015). Over the past two decades, Muntinlupa has turned into a city with fast-growing

commercial areas, as a number of factories transferred to industrial parks in nearby Laguna province. The emergence of business districts also helped Muntinlupa's economy become more service oriented (Ecological Profile of Muntinlupa, 2016). The development of Muntinlupa and the rise of subdivisions and factories in Cavite, Laguna and Batangas provinces have resulted in traffic congestion on SLEx despite the construction of Skyway (an elevated expressway built along SLEx) and other roads in the city.

The congestion is not confined to Muntinlupa. Metro Manila has become the most congested natural city with a population of at least 5 million in developing Asia (Asian Development Bank Outlook Update, 2019). The distinction was based on travel time between randomly selected hot spots during peak hours.

The economic cost alone of traffic congestion in Metro Manila was estimated at P3.5 billion daily in 2017 and would rise to P5.4 billion daily if nothing is done (Japan International Cooperation Agency, 2017). Traffic congestion is also an environmental and a public health issue. Greenhouse gas emissions from vehicles contribute to climate change while long-term exposure to vehicle exhaust is associated with respiratory and other health problems and deaths (Milman, 2021).

The traffic congestion highlights the need for additional transport infrastructure in the metropolis, which has seen a rapid rise in the number of vehicles, particularly motorcycles, as populations and incomes grow. Over the past several years projects have been implemented to address the huge transport infrastructure deficit in Metro Manila. Notable projects are:

- Ninoy Aquino International Airport Expressway (De Guzman, 2017) and Laguna Lake Highway (Banzon, 2018) were opened to traffic.
- C-5 was extended from Taguig City to Parañaque and is being connected

to Manila-Cavite Expressway (Rey, 2021).

- Two subway systems in Metro Manila (PhilStar Global, 2019) are in the works (Camus, 2021), and the northward extension of Philippine National Railways to Clark in Pampanga province and its southward extension to Calamba City in Laguna province are in the pipeline (Railway Technology, 2022).
- A new mass rail transit line, a light rail transit extension and additional bridges on the Pasig River are being built.
- Skyway has been extended from Buendia in Makati to Balintawak in Quezon City, connecting SLEx to North Expressway and cutting travel time (Manabat, 2021).

Extended too was Skyway's opposite end in the south to avoid the congestion at the Alabang viaduct in Muntinlupa (Abadilla, 2021). The city also benefited from Muntinlupa-Cavite Expressway that linked SLEx to Daang Hari (Tabano, 2015) and from a road network linking several of its subdivisions.

The finished projects have sped up travel in certain parts of Metro Manila at certain hours of the day, but traffic congestion has persisted as traffic expands to fill available road capacity.

Besides its economic, environmental and health costs, the traffic problem also affects land prices. Land in more accessible areas command higher prices than those that face accessibility issues.

Statement of the Problem

“How did an environmental force, the City Alternative Route Entry and Exit System (CARES), influence land prices in Pleasant Village?” is the main research

question. The study also addresses the question, “How did certain political and economic forces influence land prices in the subdivision?”

Estimating the influence of a new road like CARES on the value of adjacent or nearby real estate, however, poses a challenge to appraisers. The three valuation approaches—sales comparison, cost and income—are inappropriate for measuring the effect of a new road on property. Appraisers as well as developers, urban planners and government agencies can use the difference-in-differences method or the before-and-after comparison to isolate the influence of the transport facility on the value of land. This method identifies a test group, areas near the facility, and a control group, which is farther away and thus considered not affected by the infrastructure.

Objectives of the Study

The study aims to examine the roles played by environmental forces in the surge of land prices over the past several years in a private subdivision in the southernmost city of Metro Manila. The study focuses on how a new road network, CARES, an environmental factor, which was built to address traffic congestion, another environmental factor, has influenced the property market in the subdivision.

How certain political and economic forces affect market values of properties in the subdivision will also be examined. The study also looks into how the road network came about because of government directives, economic development and community actions over the past few decades, providing a historical context. The case study method is used to find out how the alternative route, which arose from linking existing roads of adjacent subdivisions by knocking down sections of walls separating them to allow residents to bypass a congested national highway, pushed up land prices in a subdivision hosting CARES.

Significance of the Study

The alternative route for several subdivisions in Muntinlupa demonstrates that easing congestion need not be as expensive as building a new transport infrastructure. The study is also significant for another reason. Samples of land sale in Pleasant and Greenheights show the positive effect of the transport infrastructure on properties nearby.

The total value of the capitalization of the transport infrastructure into land prices in Pleasant was estimated and compared with the cost of building it, giving city officials and planners an idea of the economic benefits and bigger tax base brought about by the access road.

Clearly, the main beneficiaries of the road are landowners who saw the values of their property rise substantially as a result of improved accessibility. The city government that built the access road can consider getting a share of the landowners' windfall by raising their property tax. Levies can also be collected from business owners and motorists who benefited from lower transportation cost due to the new route.

Scope and Limitation

The study focuses on increases in land prices in a test subdivision--between 2010 (three years before CARES initially opened to traffic) and 2016 (two years after the alternative route came into service for good), and between 2016 and 2019 (a year after the third phase of the road opened).

Though this is a case study in which one community will do, another subdivision was added to heed the advice to get a second community as a test group. One subdivision was chosen as a control group.

An estimate of the total capitalization of CARES into land prices in Pleasant was based on land prices declared in the deeds of absolute sale before and after the route opened to traffic, on the average lot size and on the total number of lots according to the subdivision plan.

The total number of land sales from which samples were drawn could not be determined as the deeds of absolute sale were not all registered with the City Assessor's Office in the year these were notarized. It was also found that the list of transactions was not solely for the sale of property. The transactions included deeds of donation, extrajudicial settlements, affidavits of self-adjudication and correction of names. As a result, the pool of land transfers from which samples could be drawn was reduced.

Because the specifications of the alternative route could not be obtained from city hall or the Commission on Audit, the study had to measure the length and width of the road in Pleasant.

The average lot size was set at 300 sq. m., the most common cut in the subdivision. A few parcels of land, especially corner ones, exceeded 300 sq. m. and a few others were smaller than the usual lot size. The number of lots in Pleasant was arrived at by excluding areas in the subdivision plan that were eaten up by the extension of SLEx from Alabang to Canlubang, Laguna.

Data on congestion delays and travel time came from residents of Pleasant and neighboring subdivisions, and not from odometers and stopwatches of participants in a structured study of commuting in the city and beyond.

Figure 1. Muntinlupa and other cities of Metro Manila.

Figure 2. Central Business District of Muntinlupa at sunrise.

Photo by Allan Balila

Figure 3. South Luzon Expressway and Filinvest City Interchange (foreground).

Photo by Allan Balila

Figure 4. Pleasant and environs.

Source: OpenStreetMap

Chapter II

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Review of Literature

Studies of transport capitalization have sought to find out whether values of property near highways, interchanges, or mass transit stations are higher than those farther afield (Landis et al., 1994). A number of studies used the before-and-after comparison in which test and control areas were employed to isolate the influence attributed to the transport facility. Areas near the transport infrastructure constituted the test group while an area farther away was the control group, which was considered not to be affected by the facility. Differences in land prices over time in the test and control groups were presumably due to the transport infrastructure's effect. Results show that properties close by transport facilities generally command premium values.

Proximity

A review of the findings of studies on the influence of expressways on land values in Houston and Dallas found that proximity to a highway was associated with higher property values. Accessibility was measured in terms of distance of property from bands of properties in Houston and Dallas, starting with those adjacent to the expressway right of way on each side. Land values in two zones near Houston's Gulf Freeway rose 441 percent and 120 percent, respectively, between 1945-46 (when the expressway was under construction) and 1954-56 (after the expressway opened to traffic). In contrast, land values in control areas not influenced by the freeway declined 27 percent, resulting in an inferred expressway effect of 468 percent for Group 1

(immediately adjacent to the expressway) and 147 percent for Group 2, which is adjacent to Group 1 and parallel to the freeway (Adkins, 1959).

Along the Dallas Central Expressway, the net influence on the value of land adjacent to the expressway was estimated at 563 percent between 1946-50 (construction period for the most part) and 1951-55. A portion of the road chosen for the study opened to traffic in early 1953. There was hardly an increase in prices in the control areas (Adkins, 1959).

In another part of Texas, prices of unimproved properties of the test area near Interstate Highway 45 in Huntsville were also higher than those farther away, or the control area. The highway opened in 1960 (Buffington, 1967).

In Indianapolis, Indiana, the construction of an interchange between I-65 and I-465, among other factors, had positively influenced land values. "The amount of the increase was affected by nearness to an interchange, nearness to the city, completeness of the interchange, and strategic location of the property relative to its potential use as a commercial, motorist service land use" (Brown & Michael, 1973). At the same time, increases in land values slowed down with distance from an interchange.

Residential properties adjacent to modern highways, such as Park-Presidio Boulevard in California and US 50 in Lawrenceville, Illinois, were also found to have rapid increases in value than similar properties not close by (Goldstein, 1963).

Not all increases in property values though could be established as the effect of the construction of a transport infrastructure.

In North Carolina, property values on three sections of Interstate Routes I-95, I-40 and I-85 in three counties increased significantly, but the increases could not be attributed to the transport infrastructures. "[T]he controlled-access facilities under

investigation have done little to stimulate or depress surrounding property values and development during the study periods” (Cribbins et al., 1962). The study tested the hypothesis that land value decreases with an increasing distance from the highway after it was built, and that land value follows no pattern with respect to the Interstate route before it came into service. Two sections opened to traffic in 1958 and the third one in 1960.

Paved Streets

It does not take a huge investment in a transport infrastructure to trigger an increase in the value of property. Upgrading streets did the trick in a metropolitan area in southeast Mexico.

In an experiment, paving randomly selected streets in Acayucan City led to an increase in values not only of residential properties on these roads but also of those on unpaved ones. With distance from the nearest paved road reduced, values of houses on unpaved streets went up, albeit at a much lower rate. It was found that because of the government project, households on paved streets invested more in home improvements than those in the control group.

A professional appraiser estimated that the values of houses on the upgraded streets had gone up 16-17 percent. Total gains in value increased to 180 percent of street-pavement costs once spillovers to properties on unpaved streets were taken into account (Gonzales-Navarro & Quintana-Domeque, 2010).

Catchment Area

Proximity to mass rapid transit also has, by and large, positively affected property values. A review of literature on the effect of rail transit on property values

that covered 61 studies found significant positive impact of access to this mode of transportation, although at varying degrees. In developing countries, residential properties in a catchment area -- those 100 meters to 1.6 kilometers (km) from a station -- saw a five-percent increase in value. For commercial properties, the average premium was 30 percent (Abiad et al., 2019).

In Metro Manila, the value of land within 1 km of a Metro Rail Transit 3 (MRT 3) station was higher than for parcels more than 2 km away, although both posted substantial increases. MRT 3, a 16.9-km line with 13 stations, traverses five cities. One of the three mass rapid transit lines in the metropolis, MRT 3 opened in 2000.

An estimate of the impact on land values within 1 km of MRT 3 stations was conservatively placed at close to ₱180 billion or \$3.4 billion, about five times the construction cost of the commuter line. “[J]ust one-fifth of the incremental land value increase due to MRT 3 would have been enough to pay for the \$655 million total cost of MRT 3, while still leaving a very substantial windfall for private property owners.” (Abiad et al., 2019).

The capitalization of transport infrastructure has given rise to land-value capture, a mechanism that “aims to recover the value of benefits received by property owners or developers” (Zhao & Levinson, 2012) through property taxes, special assessments, joint ventures and other schemes to help fund the project (Buensuceso & Purisima, 2018).

Quality of Service

Just because a transport facility was built does not mean that values of properties nearby would go up substantially. Demand or usage matters, too. This phenomenon was observed in Miami, Florida, which is oriented around the car as a

transport mode and lacks a large CBD. With low ridership, the Miami Metrorail System had a minimal impact on residential property values (Gatzlaff & Smith, 1993).

Similarly, in areas already served by other transport facilities, a new mass rail transit will likely have a weak effect on property values.

The quality of service can, nevertheless, lead to increases in home prices, according to a study of heavy and light-rail systems in California. Regional systems such as BART are more likely to generate significant capitalization effects as they provide reliable, frequent and speedy service, serve a large market area and capture that market by providing parking. By contrast, systems that provide limited service, serve a limited market, lack parking for suburban commuters, operate at slower speeds, or do not help reduce freeway congestion are unlikely to generate significant capitalization benefits (Landis et al., 1994).

Negative Externalities

Being too near a transport facility may pull down values because of negative externalities – noise or air pollution. Land and residential homes in Indianapolis saw declines in value because of the nuisance effect of an interstate. The properties were bordered by the transport infrastructure (Brown & Michael, 1973).

Externalities also weighed down the increase in property values in Fairfax County, Virginia. Results of a 17-year longitudinal time series until 1978 showed that values of residential single-family dwellings adjacent to the Washington Capital Beltway in North Springfield, increased slowly compared with those beyond the boundary of the impact zone, or more than 343 meters from the highway.

“Traffic volumes on I-495 (level of externality) have increased quite dramatically and, without any doubt, people have become much more cognizant and

concerned about environmental issues, including traffic-generated noise and air-pollutants, since the environmental movement began approximately with Earth Day in 1969” (Langley, 1981).

Accessibility

Besides externalities, accessibility issues can also affect values of property. An interchange or a major thoroughfare may be near a residential or commercial property but may take some time to get there because of hindrances, traffic stops and congestion. In the case of a mass transit station, poor pedestrian, bicycle, or transportation connections may impede access.

Homes that have easy links to congested-free highways or mass rail transit stations are thus expected to have higher values because accessibility leads to faster travel time, lower transportation costs and other benefits like reducing commuter stress. “Except for the impacts of other factors (e.g., land use regulations, level of service), the positive transportation–property value relationship is usually found when transportation access measures accurately reflect travel time savings,” (Hou, 2017).

Middle Class

Hou found that accessibility to jobs of a single-family housing market in Los Angeles County as measured either by congested or free-flow travel time positively affected housing prices. Middle class households are willing to pay more for homes to avoid locations with high congestion delays and accessibility loss (Hou, 2017).

Many in the middle class in “superstar cities,” however, “can no longer afford to live within reasonable distance of their workplaces” and are forced to take up less expensive residences farther out of the urban center (Florida, 2017).

Before the pandemic, highly paid knowledge workers and the rich acquired property in Los Angeles, New York, London, Hong Kong and Paris, and in technology and knowledge hubs, such the San Francisco Bay Area, Boston, Amsterdam and Berlin, driving up housing prices. Priced out in some of the most vibrant and innovative neighborhoods of London, Paris and New York were not only blue-collar and service workers and the poor, but also many in the middle class (Florida, 2017).

Based on the review of related materials, it appears that no studies have been conducted on the capitalization of interconnecting streets of several residential subdivisions into land values and prices. The new corridor in Pleasant provides entry and exit points other than those via a congested national road and connects the neighboring communities to a CBD where an interchange is located. This case study will address the research gap and look into how an alternative entry and exit route affected land prices in a subdivision that sits right next to a CBD but was separated from it for decades until part of the perimeter wall was torn down to give way to the new route.

Theoretical Framework

In capitalization theory, the market value of a new or improved transport infrastructure is transmitted or “capitalized” into the values of nearby or adjacent properties due to the facility’s economic benefits, mainly improvement in accessibility (Landis et al., 1994).

Consumers, who value access to an interchange or a transit station, would pay a premium for nearby property, pushing prices up. As a result, values of land or houses near the transport infrastructure should be significantly higher than the values of comparable property far from the facility.

At the core of contemporary urban economics is the assumption that accessibility is capitalized into property values.

“Urban location and density models developed by Alonso (1964), Mills (1967, 1972) and Muth (1969) describe how and why firms and households bid up the prices of accessible sites. The result of the bidding process, at least in a monocentric city, is the classical, negative exponential density/land rent gradient,” (Landis et al., 1994) in which land values decline as one moves away from the city center.

Correspondingly, property values go up when transport costs, incurred to overcome the “friction of space,” decline (Haig, 1926). As a transport network improves, friction is reduced, bringing about accessibility advantages, or shorter travel time.

The city center attracts the highest values and rent (economic return) because its transport facilities maximize labor availability, customer flow and proximate linkages (Kivell, 1993). For business, economic return drops the farther one gets from the center to compensate for the declining revenue-earning capability and higher transport cost (Alonso, 1964).

Capitalization theory predicts that outward transportation extensions should be followed by higher suburban land values as improvements in accessibility are quickly capitalized (Landis et al., 1994).

Chapter III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Case Study

This investigation uses the case study method in explaining the surge in land prices in a subdivision after an alternative route was opened to bypass a congested road. It asks the “how” question to trace over time factors that led to the changes not only in Pleasant and its surroundings, but also in Muntinlupa City and even Metro Manila.

The case study, the preferred method of examining contemporary events when the relevant behaviors cannot be manipulated, shares many techniques of the historical method but adds two sources of evidence: “direct observation of the events being studied and interviews of the persons involved in the events” (Yin, 2003).

The case study’s ability to deal with a range of evidence from documents and artifacts to interviews and observations is considered its unique strength.

In addition, case studies are generalizable to theoretical propositions, not to populations or universes. Like the experiment, a case study does not represent a “sample” but aims to “expand and generalize theories (analytic generalization) and not to enumerate frequencies (statistical generalization),” Yin said. The goal of even a single case study is to “generalizing” and not “particularizing” analysis (Lipset et al., 1956).

In analytic generalization, the template is a previously developed theory “with which to compare empirical results of the case study. If two or more cases studies are shown to support the same theory, replication may be claimed” (Yin, 2003).

Difference in Differences

This study also uses the difference-in-differences method for the test and control subdivisions to estimate CARES' influence on land prices in Pleasant and Greenheights. The method compares changes over time in a group affected by a project with changes over time in an unaffected group. The difference in differences between the two groups are then attributed to the effect of the project (Stuart et al., 2014).

The study uses primary and secondary data gathering. Direct observations during numerous visits to Pleasant and nearby subdivisions were done, and interviews with persons knowledgeable about these communities and the city were conducted. The informants included officials and staff of the Pleasant Village Homeowners Association (PVHOA), residents, property buyers, sellers, agents and brokers, city officials (a councilor, a city assessor and the head of the city traffic management office), residents of neighboring communities and the president of another subdivision.

A Bureau of Internal Revenue (BIR) district officer and an appraiser tapped by the bureau in helping revise zonal values for Muntinlupa were also interviewed.

The study also made use of maps of Pleasant, the city road network and Metro Manila. Documents such as the series of zonal values, comprehensive land use plans, ecological profile of the city, ordinances and a memorandum of agreement between Muntinlupa and a private developer were consulted. These were supplemented by data from the central bank, the national statistics agency, and from news reports in print and articles available online.

Sampling Technique

Assessor's Office

Samples of land prices in the subdivisions before and after CARES opened were obtained from the Assessor's Office of Muntinlupa City, which keeps copies of documents of property transactions as bases for the issuance of tax declarations and collection of real property taxes.

The total number of land sales in 2010, 2016 and 2019 from which samples were drawn could not be determined as the DOAS were not all registered with the City Assessor's Office in the year these were notarized.

Nine subdivisions that have access to CARES and three without were initially considered for the test and control groups. After submitting a request to the acting assessor through the mayor, the data officer of the City Assessor's Office generated property transactions, coming up with a table of the total yearly transactions from 2009 to 2021.

For the possible control group (no access to CARES), data showed that only Lakeview 1 had a viable number of transactions from which a sample of land sales could be drawn. Among the test subdivisions, two were excluded because the transactions were mostly for houses and lots. The subdivisions--Soldiers Hills Village and Mutual Homes -- are government mass-housing projects that were already heavily built up.

In addition, an initial sample supposedly only for the sale of lots in Soldiers Hills yielded transactions that included improvements, suggesting that the sale of just land in the village were fewer than the data showed.

The lack of specific addresses of properties in the test and control groups also meant that ocular inspection of improvements on each lot sold could not be conducted

to get the value of land using the residual technique. The Assessor's Office declined to provide the addresses (only streets and block numbers) on data privacy considerations.

For the privately developed subdivisions, Camella 1, 2, 2D and 2E were excluded because land transactions in the period of study—2010, 2016 and 2019 -- were few from which samples could be drawn. The same was true for RCE, a small subdivision.

Test and Control Groups

Given the limitations in these subdivisions, the study focused on Pleasant and Greenheights as the test groups, and on Lakeview as the control subdivision.

The study later found that the list of transactions, which served as the universe from which samples could be drawn, was not solely for the sale of property. The transactions ranged from deeds of donation, extrajudicial settlements and *dacion en pago* to affidavits of self-adjudication, correction of names and DOAS. A few transactions were found to be without attachments.

Moreover, the date when transaction documents were submitted to the Assessor's Office for registration, the basis of the list from which samples were drawn, did not correspond with the date of the actual transaction. The entry dates that the Assessor's Office recorded in its database were off by months and occasionally by a few years from the date of the actual transactions (when the deed of absolute sale was notarized).

This can be explained by the lag time in selling the property and getting it titled. Owners go to the Assessor's Office to have their properties registered only after they

obtained a certificate authorizing registration from the BIR and a new title under their name from the Register of Deeds – a process that takes a few months.

Software, Manual Retrieval

It was also learned that the exact date of the transfer, donation or extrajudicial settlement was not covered by the city's real property administration system. A software, developed by the private firm SPIDC that the Assessor's Office uses, handles only data found on the tax declaration (F. Muñoz, personal communication, July 19, 2022), such as tax declaration number, transaction type, property identification number, name and address of the owner/s, location of the property, number and date of the title, lot and block number, actual use and assessed value.

To determine when a transaction of a chosen sample transpired, the Assessor's Office had to retrieve hard copies of documents from the archives -- a laborious and slow method made more challenging by the Covid-19 pandemic, even as the office performed its primary functions. As a result, data gathering of sales transactions for this study came in fits and starts, taking nine months.

There were five land transactions recorded in 2010, 20 in 2016 and 11 in 2019 for Pleasant; 17 in 2010, 27 in 2016 and 38 in 2019 for Greenheights; and 12 in 2010, 12 in 2016 and five in 2019 for Lakeview.

Rounds of Sampling

Because transactions in the records of the Assessor's Office included non-sale activities, which the study had thought to be all land sales, the pool of land transfers gathered for this study that took place in 2010 (three years before CARES initially

opened to traffic), 2016 (two years after the road came into service for good), and 2019 (a year after the third leg of CARES opened to traffic) was reduced.

This called for a second round of sampling for the test and control subdivisions to find additional sale transactions. Five samples in each subdivision were randomly drawn in the first round. In the second round, sampling was no longer random. The preferred samples were from transactions in the second semester, especially those close to December.

The study even included transactions that the Assessor's Office recorded in the first few months of 2011, 2017 and 2020 to account for the time lag between getting a new title and registering it with the Assessor's Office in hopes that sales and thus prices could, in fact, be for 2010, 2016 and 2019. The number of samples in the second round ranged from four to nine for every subdivision from the remaining transactions on the list for 2010, 2016 and 2019.

The first round for Lakeview yielded no sale for 2016 and the second produced just two, one of which was an outlier. Two outlier prices also cropped up in Pleasant for 2016. Besides the outliers, a few transactions in Pleasant and Greenheights covering several lots were excluded, limiting the scope of the data gathering to the sale of a single parcel of land. A third round of sampling for Lakeview was conducted, as only two DOAS came up in the second round.

Prices from Agents

Another set of prices, but just for Pleasant, was earlier obtained from real estate agents, licensed brokers, officers and employees of PVHOA, property owners and residents of the subdivision.

Figure 5. CARES and nearby subdivisions.

Source: "Muntinlupa: A City that Cares," City Government of Muntinlupa, 2022

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Land prices in Pleasant have soared despite its lack of amenities and other shortcomings. Prices took off after the opening of the route that bypasses the city's congested national highway. The route connects Pleasant to a CBD, transport hubs and an interchange.

The new road network came about partly because of a directive from a Philippine President for city governments to open roads in private subdivisions to nonresident motorists to help ease traffic congestion in Metro Manila. Taking a cue from the country's chief executive, a councilor in Muntinlupa sponsored an ordinance to build an access road by connecting several subdivisions to the CBD. Residents of several communities adversely affected by the worsening congestion then formed a group to push for the implementation of the ordinance, a process that took more than a decade to come to fruition.

Other developments also came into play. The privatization of a large tract of public land in Barangay Alabang in the early 1990s to help shore up the finances of the national government and the property's subsequent transformation into a thriving commercial area have had knock-on effects, including rising property prices, in neighboring areas.

Despite low interest rates before the pandemic, bank financing did not figure prominently in real estate transactions in Pleasant.

BIR and CARES

Before CARES was built, land values as measured by the zonal value, which the BIR uses for charging sellers of real estate the 6-percent capital gains tax, were not moving for both Pleasant and Lakeview. The zonal value for Pleasant in 2007 and 2010 was P2,400 per sq. m. For Lakeview the zonal value was stuck at P1,900 per sq. m. during the period. These values did not change until June 2014, not long after CARES was built, when the BIR raised the zonal value in Pleasant to P12,000 per sq. m.

The BIR included a picture of the newly built CARES leading to Filinvest City in its letter to then PVHOA president Danny Garcia, inviting him to a public hearing sometime in the second half of 2013 on the proposed revision of zonal values in the city.

He objected to the BIR's proposed zonal value of P20,000 per sq. m. for Pleasant because it would make land in the subdivision unattractive to prospective buyers (D. Garcia, personal communication, Feb. 2, 2018). Besides, there are many idle lots in the subdivision with varying contours--from those on a cliff and elevated areas to less steep and flatter areas on the main and inner roads. "And you're saying P20,000 for all lots? Nobody would buy the land. You'll just make us miserable," he recalled telling the BIR at the hearing.

Asked about the bases for the steep increase in the zonal value, the BIR cited the area's proximity to a church, mall, presence of a grocery store and supermarket, good roads and facilities, including security guards, as well as a school bus service. "We have a school but lacked most of those," countered Garcia. "*Sige*, noted," came the reply of a BIR official.

The objections of the PVHOA worked to moderate the increase. The BIR set the zonal value for Pleasant at P12,000 per sq. m. starting June 14, 2014, still a 400-percent jump from the previous level. Had Pleasant not pose objections, its zonal value would have skyrocketed by 733 percent.

The zonal value for Lakeview rose 321 percent to P8,000 per sq. m.

Figure 6. Zonal values in Pleasant and Lakeview: 2007-2016.

Price Surge

The price increases for lots in Pleasant after CARES opened to traffic were more pronounced in sales data collected from real estate practitioners and residents than the prices that sellers declare in DOAS.

A possible explanation for this phenomenon is the practice among certain sellers to declare a price at the same level as that of the zonal value, which in Pleasant lags behind market prices. The aim is to minimize the amount paid for the 6-percent capital gains tax to the BIR, which requires sellers to pay the tax based on the zonal value or the selling price, whichever is higher.

Sales Data

Lots were selling in Pleasant for P3, 500 to P5,000 per sq. m. until 2013 (D. Carandang, personal communication, Feb. 7, 2018). Several months after the opening of CARES, a lot was sold for P5,000 per sq. m. on Regent Street and another parcel of land for P8,000 per sq. m. on Peninsula Street in 2014.

By 2015, a lot on Peninsula Street fetched a price of P12,000 per sq. m., matching the new zonal value, which by then had increased substantially. The following year a parcel of land on Mandarin Avenue changed hands for P13,000 per sq. m. Then the price progressively rose to P15,000 per sq. m. (Mandarin), P16,000 per sq. m. (Intercon) and P17,000 per sq. m. (corner of Regent and Hyatt) in 2017. By 2018 and 2019, the market price further went up to P20,000 per sq. m.

One transaction bucked the upward trend. A lot was sold for P18,000 per sq. m. in December 2020, a drop in price that may be explained by the property's location at the end of Holiday Inn Street. The lot is right beside SLEx and the then ongoing construction of the extension of the southern terminus of Skyway, with the attendant

negative externalities -- noise, air and light pollution from thousands of vehicles barreling along the expressway night and day.

Pandemic

In 2021, two transactions saw land prices rising to P25,000 per q. m. and to P31,000 per sq. m., up 520 percent from the P5,000 per sq. m. in 2014 before CARES permanently opened. Both lots are in a relatively quiet area on Intercon Street.

The transactions suggest that the capitalization of the new route into the prices of property in Pleasant has not been blunted by the pandemic. Covid-19 may even have the unintended effect of enhancing the value of land in the subdivision because its open spaces and greenery offer some relief from cabin fever due to quarantine.

TABLE 1*Price of Lots in Pleasant from 2013 to 2021*

Year	Price in pesos	Area	Street
	Up to 2013	P3, 500-P5,000	Village in general
2014	5, 000 8, 000	300 300	Regent Peninsula
2015	12, 000	336	Peninsula
2016	12, 000 13, 000	204 300	Regent Mandarin
2017	15, 000 16, 000 17, 000	300 300 700+	Mandarin Intercon Regent cor. Hyatt
2018	18, 000 20, 000 20, 000 20, 000	300 300 336 325	Mandarin Mandarin Regent Regent
2019	20, 000	300	Mandarin
2020	18, 000	300*	Holiday Inn
2021	25, 000 31, 000	360 300	Intercon Intercon

*Beside an expressway

Note: Data from agents, brokers, buyers, sellers, and officials and employees of PVHOA.

Figure 7. Prices of lots in Pleasant from 2013 to 2021.

Table 2

Percentage change in prices in Pleasant in 2013-2016, 2013-2019, and 2013-2021

Subdivision	2013-2016	2013-2019	2013-2021
Pleasant	194	371	559

Note: Data from agents, brokers, buyers, sellers, and officials and employees of PVHOA

Figure 8. Access road in Pleasant from Filinvest City.

Photo by JVS

Figure 9. Entrance to Filinvest City from Pleasant.

Photo by JVS

Figure 10. Corporate Avenue a few meters from CARES' Filinvest Gate.

Photo by JVS

Amid the price surge, bank financing hardly figured in the transactions. The sale is on cash basis – no installment or bank loans – because sellers do not want a tedious process of closing a sale. “If the process takes some time, other buyers [who are ready to pay in cash] could come in and get the property,” said Garcia (2018), who had facilitated the sale of several lots in the village. Another long-time resident of Pleasant said all the sales she had arranged were in cash (L. Huiso, personal communication, Feb. 7, 2018).

Deeds of Absolute Sale

Prices that buyers and sellers declare in DOAS also rose, although not at the same pace as those shared by real estate practitioners and residents in Pleasant.

Table 3

Average Prices in Pleasant, Greenheights and Lakeview in 2010, 2016 and 2019

Subdivision	2010	2016	2019
Pleasant	P2, 122/sq. m.	12, 079	12, 109
Greenheights	2, 536	5, 027	9, 165
Lakeview	1, 588	5, 900	7, 171

Note: Basic data from the Assessor's Office of Muntinlupa City

Figure 11. Average prices in Pleasant, Greenheights and Lakeview: 2016 and 2019.

Table 4

Percentage Change in Prices in Pleasant, Greenheights and Lakeview in 2010-2016, 2016-2019

Subdivision	2010-2016	2016-2019
Pleasant	469	< 1
Greenheights	98	82
Lakeview	272	21

In contrast, Lakeview, the subdivision that has no access to CARES, exhibited lower price increases over the same period. Prices went up from P1, 588 per sq. m. in 2010 to P5, 900 in 2016, and to P7, 171 in 2019.

Data from the Assessor's Office show that prices of lots in Pleasant rose 469 percent from an average of P2, 122 per sq. m. in 2010 to P12, 079 per sq. m. in 2016, an increase of P9, 957 per sq. m. The price in 2019, however, was P12, 109 per sq. m., almost the same as that of 2016.

By 2019, the third phase of CARES had been opened for a year, allowing two more subdivisions, including Greenheights, to use the new route and helping ease congestion on the national road. Most private vehicles of the subdivisions were by then taking the alternative route.

In Greenheights, the average land prices climbed from P2, 536 per sq. m. in 2010 to P5, 027 in 2016 (when it had yet to gain access to CARES) and to P9,165 in 2019.

Price Increase Due to the New Road

Using the difference-in-differences method, the price increase presumably

attributed to CARES in Pleasant was **P5, 645 per sq. m. in 2016**. Three years later it declined to P4, 404 per sq. m.

Prices rose in Greenheights by P2, 867 per sq. m. between 2016 and 2019, presumably because of CARES. The alternative route had a negative effect on prices in the subdivision between 2010 and 2016, when it still had no access to CARES.

Table 5

Pleasant and Lakeview Prices in 2010 and 2016

Subdivision	2010	2016	Difference
Pleasant	P2, 122/ sq. m.	12, 079*	P9, 957
Lakeview	1, 588**	5, 900**	4, 312
Difference	534	6, 179	5, 645

*Note: *Two outliers and the sale of multiple lots in a transaction were excluded in computing the average price.*

*** An outlier was excluded.*

Table 6

Pleasant and Lakeview Prices in 2010 and 2016, Including Outliers and Sale of Multiple Lots

Subdivision	2010	2016	Difference
Pleasant	P2, 176/ sq. m.	19, 094	P16, 918
Lakeview	2, 240	7, 774	5, 534
Difference	-64	11, 320	11, 384

Table 7*Pleasant and Lakeview Prices in 2010 and 2019*

Subdivision	2010	2019	Difference
Pleasant	P2, 122	12,109	9, 987
Lakeview	1, 588*	7, 171	5, 583
Difference	534	4, 938	4, 404

*Note: * An outlier was excluded*

Table 8*Pleasant and Lakeview Prices in 2010 and 2019, Including a Lakeview Outlier*

Subdivision	2010	2019	Difference
Pleasant	P2, 176	12, 088	9, 912
Lakeview	2, 240	7, 171	4, 931
Difference	-64	4, 917	4, 981

Table 9*Greenheights and Lakeview Prices in 2010 and 2016*

Subdivision	2010	2016	Difference
Greenheights	2, 536	5, 027	2, 491
Lakeview	1, 588*	5, 900*	4, 312
Difference	948	-873	-1, 821

*Note: *An outlier was excluded*

Table 10*Greenheights and Lakeview Prices in 2010 and 2016, Including an Outlier in Lakeview*

Subdivision	2010	2016	Difference
Greenheights	2, 536	5, 027	2, 491
Lakeview	2, 240	7, 772	5, 532
Difference	296	-2, 745	- 3, 041

Table 11*Greenheights and Lakeview Prices in 2016 and 2019*

Subdivision	2016	2019	Difference
Greenheights	5, 027	9, 165*	4, 138
Lakeview	5, 900*	7, 171	1, 271
Difference	-873	1, 994	2, 867

*Note: *Outliers were excluded***Table 12***Greenheights and Lakeview Prices in 2016 and 2019*

Subdivision	2016	2019	Difference
Greenheights	5, 027	8, 522 *	3, 495
Lakeview	7, 772 *	7, 171	- 601
Difference	-2, 745	1, 351	4, 096

*Note: * Including outliers in Lakeview in 2016
and in Greenheights in 2019*

Table 13*Greenheights and Lakeview Prices in 2010 and 2019*

Subdivision	2010	2019	Difference
Greenheights	2, 536	9, 165*	6, 629
Lakeview	1, 588*	7, 171	5, 583
Difference	948	1, 994	1, 046

Note: * An outlier was excluded

Table 14*Greenheights and Lakeview Prices in 2010 and 2019, Including Outliers*

Subdivision	2010	2019	Difference
Greenheights	2, 536	8, 522	5, 986
Lakeview	2, 240	7, 171	4, 931
Difference	296	1, 351	1, 055

Including outliers and the sale of several lots in one transaction in 2016 in Pleasant, and an outlier in 2016 in Lakeview and in 2019 in Greenheights results in different estimates, which nevertheless indicate the positive influence of CARES on prices in the test subdivisions.

The estimated increase in land prices in Pleasant between 2010 and 2016 was **P5, 645 per sq. m.** when the outliers and sale of multiple lots per transaction were excluded. When the outliers and sale of multiple lots were included, the increase was

much higher at P11, 384 per sq. m. The increase between 2010 and 2019 stood at P4, 404 per sq. m. when an outlier was excluded.

As for Greenheights, CARES negatively affected prices between 2010 and 2016, when the subdivision still had no access to the alternative road. But by 2019, a year after the subdivision gained access to the route, prices rose to P2, 867 per sq. m. when outliers were excluded and to P4, 096 per sq. m. when outliers were included.

Capitalization

The increase in prices in Pleasant and Greenheights shows that CARES has been capitalized into land prices in the subdivisions.

For Pleasant alone, the capitalization is estimated at **P476 million** in 2016. Each lot with an average cut of 300 sq. m. gained P5, 645 sq. m., or P1. 7 million in value between 2010 and 2016. (The number of lots in the village was reduced to about 280 after the extension of SLEx to Canlubang, Laguna, ate up a portion of the subdivision as right of way.)

In 2019, the capitalization in Pleasant declined to about P1. 3 million per lot, still a huge windfall for landowners, resulting in a P364-million capitalization for all residential land in the village.

Figure 12. Lot plan of Pleasant.

Source: PVHOA

Project Cost

The cost of the alternative route is just a fraction of the capitalization of CARES, which private contractors built on behalf of the city government in three phases in 2013, 2014 and 2018. The total cost of CARES as of 2016 is estimated at P35.5 million to P38.9 million, less than 10 percent of the capitalization of land prices in Pleasant.

The construction cost for Phase 1 is the sum of the costs to build the 74-m road with gutter and sidewalk on Mandarin Avenue at Lot 104 Block 1 in Pleasant to connect with South Corporate Avenue in Filinvest City and the 113-m section between the

walled end of Hawk Street in Camella 2 and the south end of Mandarin Avenue at the corner of Peninsula Street in Pleasant.

Construction

The construction cost in 2013 of the two sections, with a combined length of 187 meters and width of 6 meters, or a total area of 1, 122 sq. m., as measured by the author, is estimated at P1. 1 million. The estimate is based on the construction cost per square meter of a concrete road in 2022 that the Subdivision and Housing Developers Association (SHDA) applies to economic housing in Metro Manila.

The construction cost of a square meter of a concrete road, which includes drainage and sidewalk, was up to P1, 500 per sq. m. for a five-hectare subdivision (S. Ducoy, personal communication, September 28, 2022). He said a bigger subdivision would lower the cost of a concrete road because of economy of scale.

Replacement Cost New

The replacement cost new (RCN) of Phase 1 is P1, 683,000 (1, 122 sq m x P1, 500/ sq. m.). RCN less accrued depreciation for nine years (P605, 880, or P67, 320 x 9) to get its cost in 2013, gives us P1, 077, 120. The depreciation rate is 4 percent, or 100 percent divided by 25, given that the useful life of a concrete road is 25 years (Barr, 2022). The annual depreciation is P67, 320 (P1, 683, 000 x .04). Depreciating P1, 077, 120 for three years to get the cost of the road in 2016 gives us P875,160 (P1, 077, 120 – P201, 960).

Using the standard cost of P25 million to P30 million that the Department of Public Works and Highways (DPWH) set for a kilometer of a concrete two-way road in 2013 (Ager, 2013) provides a higher estimate of Phase 1's cost than the one using

SHDA data. Depreciating the P27 million in average cost per kilometer to 2016, results in P23, 760,000 (P27,000,000 - P3, 240,000 [the accrued depreciation for three years as the annual depreciation is P1, 080, 000 given a depreciation rate of 4 percent]).

The equivalent cost of 187 m of Phase 1 then is P4.44 million by 2016 (1,000 m/187 m = P23, 760, 000/x. Transposing x gives us P4, 443, 120).

Thus, the value of Phase 1 in 2016 could be somewhere between P875, 160 based on SHDA data and P4.44 million based on DPWH data, or thereabouts.

SDHA and DPWH data were used to get a sense of the cost of Phase 1 because offices of the city government of Muntinlupa, from the finance and engineering departments to the Bids and Awards Committee, could not provide the project cost of CARES and its specifications.

Neither was the cost of CARES could be gleaned from annual reports of the Commission of Audit on the finances of the city government of Muntinlupa.

The first phase was built at the time of Mayor Aldrin San Pedro, a political opponent of Jaime Fresnedi, who served his second nine-year term starting July 2013 after defeating San Pedro. Fresnedi is now congressman of the lone district of Muntinlupa.

Right of Way

The cost of land on which the road was built was estimated at P9.7 million for Pleasant (P12, 079/sq. m. x 800 sq. m.) and P20. 6 million for Filinvest City (P47, 769/sq. m. x 432), or a total of P30. 3 million by 2016. (Prices for 2016 for Pleasant were from DOAS while prices for Filinvest City in 2018 were from online real estate platforms. The Filinvest prices were discounted to 2016.)

The basis for the cost of right of way in Filinvest was the selling price of residential lots in Palms Pointe, the only subdivision in the CBD, which was adjusted for market resistance and location of the right of way. (Average offered price of P72, 250/sq. m. in Palms Pointe in 2018 less 10 percent for market resistance, or discount, and less 10 percent to account for the not so desirable location of the right of way gives us P57, 800/ sq. m. Discounting it to 2016 on the assumption that the price was rising 10 percent a year ($P57, 800/(1 + 0.1)^2$, or $PV = (0.1, 2, 57800)$) using Excel, results in P47, 769 per sq. m.

Donation

A total of 800 sq. m. in Pleasant was donated to pave the way for the construction of the road and Filinvest Land Inc. allowed the use of 432 sq. m. at the end of Filinvest City's South Corporate Avenue as right of way.

Adding the construction cost of between P875, 160 and P4.4 million, and the cost of land of P30.3 million gives us a total cost of between P31.2 million and P34.7 million for Phase 1. Phase 2 of CARES cost P4.58 million, the amount spent to refurbish a barangay road between Camella 2 and Camella 2D, and Soldiers Hills Village in 2014 (C. Valerio, Viber message, 2022). Depreciating it to 2016 gives us P4.2 million.

In total, Phases 1 and 2 of CARES cost P35.4 million to **P38.9 million** in 2016, or **8 percent** of the alternative route's capitalization into land values in Pleasant.

Phase 3 involved the construction of a P5.74-million bridge in 2018 to connect Soldiers Hills Village and the two southernmost subdivisions in the CARES network - Camella 1 and Greenheights.

Table 15*Pleasant Prices in 2010*

Code	Date	Area in sq. m.	Amount	Price/sq. m.	Street
TR 02883	2/8	300	P750,000	P2, 500	Peninsula
02885	2/15	150	375, 000	2, 500	Peninsula
02888	3/5	300	750, 000	2, 500	Intercon
02911	6/21	300	450, 000	1, 500	Intercon
02890	8/6	300	340, 000	1, 133	-----
02887	11/15	358	930, 800	2, 598	Pen. cor. Hyatt

Average price: **P2, 122** per sq. m.

Table 16*Pleasant Prices in 2016**

Code	Date	Area in sq. m.	Amount	Price/sq. m.	Street
TR 01897	9/4	286	P3, 500,000	P12, 238	Peninsula
01660	10/_	300	3, 600, 000	12, 000	Mandarin
01729	12/7	300	3, 600,000	12, 000	Intercon

Note: *Excluding outliers and sale of multiple lots

Average price: **P12, 079** per sq. m.

Table 17*Pleasant Prices in 2016, Including Outliers and Sale of Multiple Lots*

Code	Date	Area in sq. m.	Amount	Price/sq. m.	Street
TR 01652	7/21	313	P10, 956, 000	P35, 003	Mandarin
01655	7/21	300	10, 956, 000	36, 520	Mandarin
01897	9/4	286	3, 500, 000	12, 238	Peninsula
01898	10/14	2, 206 (6 lots)	15, 000, 000	6, 800	Mandarin
01660	10/_	300	3, 600, 000	12, 000	Mandarin
01729	12/7	300	3, 600,000	12, 000	Intercon

Average price: P19, 093 per sq. m.

Table 18*Pleasant Prices in 2019*

Code	Date	Area in sq. m.	Amount	Price/sq. m.	Street
TR 01751	3/4	321	P3, 500, 000	P10, 903	Peninsula
01687	5/16	336	4, 289,361.7	12, 766	Peninsula
01688	5/16	312	3, 982, 978	12, 766	Peninsula
01696	7/5	300	3, 600, 000	12, 000	Peninsula

Average price: P12, 109 per sq. m.

Table 19*Greenheights Prices in 2010*

Code	Date	Area in sq. m.	Amount	Price/sq. m.	Street
TR 02811	1/18	300	P700, 000	P 2, 333	S. Alvendia
02847	7/28	370	1, 200, 000	3, 242	
02839	8/24	300	620, 0000	2, 067	
02838	11/30	300	750, 000	2, 500	

Average price: **P2, 536** per sq. m.

Table 20*Greenheights Prices in 2016*

Code	Date	Area (sq. m.)	Amount	Price/sq. m.	Street
TR 01532	2/9	396	P1, 500, 000	P3, 788	S. Alvendia
01353	4/22	321	1, 500, 000	4, 673	S. Alvendia cor. Jasmine
01190	4/15	240	1, 632, 000	6, 800	
01205	7/20	165	1, 072, 000	6, 497	Yellow Bell
01553	7/22	360	1, 260, 000	3, 500	Wintergreen
01314	8/9	270	1, 080, 000	4, 000	Hyacinth
01275	9/16	73	474, 000	6, 493	Everlasting Circle
01165	12/8	291	1, 300, 000	4, 467	Primrose

Average price: **P5, 027** per sq. m.

Table 21*Greenheights Prices in 2019, Excluding Outliers and Sale of Multiple Lots*

Code	Date	Area in sq. m.	Amount	Price/sq. m.	Street
TR 01388	2/7	211	P2, 110, 000	10, 000	
01419	3/6	240	1, 920, 000	8, 000	Primrose
01154	5/7	382	2, 500, 000	6, 544	
01265	10/3	130	1, 300, 000	10, 000	
01430	10/18	240	2, 107, 200	8, 780	Quercus
01263	10/30	96	1, 152, 000	12, 000	S. Alvendia
01253	10/30	128	1, 536, 000	12, 000	S. Alvendia
01110	12/13	396	2, 376, 000	6, 000	Rosemary

Average price: **P9,165** per sq. m.**Table 22***Greenheights Prices in 2019, Including Outliers and Sale of Multiple Lots*

Code	Date	Area in sq. m.	Amount	Price/sq. m.	Street
TR 01388	2/7	211	P2, 110, 000	P10, 000	
01419	3/6	240	1, 920, 000	8, 000	Primrose
01154	5/7	382	2, 500, 000	6, 544	
01265	10/3	130	1, 300, 000	10, 000	
01430	10/18	240	2, 107, 200	8, 780	Quercus
01263	10/30	96	1, 152, 000	12, 000	S. Alvendia
01253	10/30	128	1, 536, 000	12, 000	S. Alvendia
01254	12/11	688	2, 000, 000	2, 907	S. Alvendia
01110	12/13	396	2, 376, 000	6, 000	Rosemary
01490	12/17	7, 580 (14 lots)	68, 124, 000	8, 987	

Average price: **8, 522/sq. m.**

Table 23*Lakeview Prices in 2010, Excluding an Outlier and Sale of Multiple Lots*

Code	Date	Area in sq. m.	Amount	Price/sq. m.	Street
TR 02300	3/18	248	P400, 000	P1, 613	
02174	3/23	130	100, 000	769	
02068	8/9	126	200, 000	1, 587	Narra
02071	11/18	63	120, 000	1, 905	
02112	12/23	218	450, 000	2, 064	Estanislao

Average price: P1, 588 per sq. m.

Table 24*Lakeview Prices in 2010, Including an Outlier*

Code	Date	Area in sq. m.	Amount	Price/sq. m.	Street
TR 02300	3/18	248	P400, 000	P1, 613	
02174	3/23	130	100, 000	769	
02068	8/9	126	200, 000	1, 587	Narra
02071	11/18	63	120, 000	1, 905	
02070	11/19	126	693, 000	5, 500	
02112	12/23	218	450, 000	2, 064	Estanislao

Average price: **P2,240** per sq. m.

Table 25*Lakeview Prices in 2016, Excluding an Outlier*

Code	Date	Area in sq. m.	Amount	Price/sq. m.	Street
TR 02304	3/15	220	P850, 000	3, 864	
02229	5/12	51	382, 000	7, 490	Estanislao
02262	12/15	58	368, 000	6, 345	Cattleya

Average price: 5, 900 per sq. m.

Note: The outlier was found to be at the corner of Genaro and Estanislao Streets. Estanislao is the main road of Lakeview. An ocular inspection found that one corner property is occupied by a store selling construction materials, soda and other goods. The property at the other corner is a two-story building with the front side formerly used as a commercial space.

Table 26*Lakeview Prices in 2016, Including an Outlier*

Code	Date	Area in sq. m.	Amount	Price/sq. m.	Street
TR 02304	3/15	220	P850, 000	3, 864	
02229	5/12	51	382, 000	7, 490	Estanislao
02242	5/20	121	1, 620, 000	13, 388	Genaro cor. Estanislao
02262	12/15	58	368, 000	6, 345	Cattleya

Average price: P7, 772 per sq. m.

Table 27*Lakeview Prices in 2019*

Code	Date	Area in sq. m.	Amount	Price/sq. m.	Street
TR 02292	2/27	60.50	P650, 000	P10, 744	
0241	6/3	400	1, 900, 000	4, 750	Mangga
02313	7/8	299	1, 800, 000	6, 020	

Average price: **P7, 171** per sq. m.

Short on Amenities

The surge in prices came even as Pleasant remained relatively undeveloped compared with other subdivisions in the southernmost city of Metro Manila. The subdivision, put up by spouses Felimon Sr. and Felisa Buenaventura, traders who had sold apples, grapes, cheese and meat at Quinta Market in Quiapo, Manila (Huiso, 2018), is not connected to Maynilad Water, although other utilities like power and telephone as well as internet and cable TV are available.

The subdivision relies on an aging deep-well system for its water supply. Areas with high elevation do not get water from the village tank because of weak pressure. So, homeowners in these areas have installed their own deep wells and pumps at considerable expense.

Water quality is also problem. Rust and sediments from old distribution lines have caused the water to turn brown, prompting residents who put up new houses to install PVC pipes on the surface so these could be easily replaced when clogged up with sediments.

Besides the lack of connection to a water concessionaire, Pleasant has inadequate streetlights and drainage system. Drainage pipes along the roads are installed only on one side, forcing residents who built houses on the other side to have pipes laid just below the surface of the concrete road to connect to the sewer.

The absence of amenities like a clubhouse, function room, lounge area, fitness gym, swimming pool or sports center is also glaring. What passes for an amenity is the covered court that the city government constructed in 2015.

Figure 13. Covered court courtesy of the city government.

Photo by JVS

Amid these deficiencies, coupled with a legal dispute between the developer and the contractor, and a case among the heirs of the Buenaventura couple, only about half of Pleasant's buildable area has improvements some 40 years after it was opened.

Opened in the second half of the seventies, Pleasant had 317 lots, mostly with a minimum cut of 300 sq m (PVHOA, 2018). The construction of SLEx from Alabang to Canlubang, Laguna, ate up about 1/8th of the total area of Pleasant, including some 35 lots. The extension of SLEx, formerly known as the South Superhighway, to Canlubang, Laguna, was completed in 1979.

Figure 14. Part of Mandarin Avenue, Pleasant's main road, that had no improvements until 2021.

Photo by JVS

Alternative Route

The lack of amenities did not discourage people from acquiring property in Pleasant. The improved accessibility, savings on fuel and less stress from commuting because of CARES overshadowed the deficiencies and made Pleasant attractive to buyers. For certain residents of Ayala Alabang, for instance, avoiding traffic congestion in their area is driving them to acquire property in Pleasant. A businessman wants to bequeath his house in Ayala Alabang to his son so he can live in Pleasant, away from the traffic congestion of Commerce Avenue or Alabang-Zapote Road (Garcia, 2018).

In contrast, it takes only a few minutes to get out of Pleasant via CARES going to Makati to the north or Calamba, Laguna, to the south. “A lot of people are buying property in Pleasant because it is easier for residents to travel [to work or to any other activity]. Its accessibility is much better than any other subdivision in Muntinlupa,” said Garcia (2018). “This is the best.”

Figure 15. Vicinity map of CARES.

Faster Commute

Not only residents of Pleasant but also of other subdivisions with access to the alternative route are enjoying faster commute. Marijo Inserto, a resident of Soldiers' Hills, no longer takes the national road on her commute. Before the pandemic, she used CARES four times daily, driving her son to and from Southridge, a school beside the entrance to Hillsborough in Barangay Cupang near the west service road in Muntinlupa. Without CARES, it used to take her some 30 minutes by car just to get to Filinvest City on the way to her son's school. Now it takes only 10 minutes (M. Inserto, personal communication, Aug. 30, 2018).

Figure 16. CARES traffic sign.

Photo by JVS

Residents of Greenheights also now enjoy faster commute. CARES has shortened travel time of residents from the subdivision to Filinvest City and Alabang market to just 15 minutes. It used to be 45 minutes to an hour (M. Escudro, personal communication, Oct. 24, 2018).

The new road network is a boon to workers. "Due to CARES, traffic congestion along the national road has eased, especially during the Christmas season. It is

beneficial to those making a living as they can reach their destinations faster and safer,” said Zeny Manrizza of Mutual Homes Phases 1 and 2 (Muntinlupa: A City that Cares, 2022), who also noted that “CARES is the quickest way to reach the sick. The road network is also the fastest route for firetrucks.”

Inserto and Manrizza are among residents whose family vehicles were issued stickers so they can use CARES. Filinvest Land Inc. issued a total of 6,000 stickers in 2021 (Geli, 2021).

Like a heart bypass that allows blood to flow unobstructed into the human circulatory system, CARES has sent vehicles of residents of Pleasant moving without congestion delay to and from Filinvest City and beyond. CARES also has allowed residents of the village to enjoy the wide and green spaces of Filinvest City, including its newly opened Central Park, by taking walks or by jogging or by riding mountain bikes on designated trails.

CARES was built to address the accessibility problem not only of Pleasant but also of other communities. From Pleasant’s single entry and exit point in the east, CARES has added two more—in the north and in the southwest that connect it to other subdivisions. The opening of CARES has given Pleasant the distinction of being the only subdivision with direct access to the CBD in Alabang, Barangay Bayanan and Barangay Putatan. CARES connected not only Pleasant but also 10 nearby subdivisions – first, the group of Soldiers, Mutual Homes (1, 2 and 3), Camella Homes (2, 2D and 2E) and RCE, and four years later, Camella 1 and Greenheights – to Filinvest City.

Figure 17. Car sticker issued by Filinvest City.

Expressway and Skyway

In Filinvest City are entry and exit gates of SLEx, ramps of Skyway and a terminal at South Station for public utility buses and jeepneys, and vans. The CBD is also connected to the Alabang - Zapote Road and Commerce Avenue that both lead to Alabang Town Center, Madrigal Business Park and Ayala Alabang Village – all in Muntinlupa, and to Las Piñas and Daang Hari Road, which leads to Bacoor and other parts of Cavite province.

As envisioned, CARES would interconnect subdivisions from Victoria Homes in Barangay Tunasan to Filinvest City. Victoria Homes was to be interconnected to Susana Heights and the New Bilibid Prison (NBP) reservation through NBP's existing road network, to Katarungan Village and Greenheights, to Camella 1, Soldiers' Hills and Camella 2, 2D and 2E, and to Pleasant and Filinvest City, and vice versa (Ordinance No. 02-045, 2002). CARES, however, has yet to be extended to Katarungan Village because of objections from homeowners, mostly employees of the Department of Justice and offices under it, such as the Bureau of Immigration, National

Bureau of Investigation and Bureau of Jail Management and Penology (D. Nolasco, personal communication, Oct. 18, 2018).

Sole Entry and Exit Point

Before CARES was built, Pleasant and neighboring subdivisions – all located right beside SLEx to the west but without direct access to it– had exits that cross the expressway through an underpass or an overpass and connect with the national road. SLEx and the national road are about parallel to each other but meet at the viaduct in Alabang.

For almost four decades, Pleasant could be reached only via Bautista Street from the national road in Barangay Bayanan. Bautista Street, which connects Pleasant for less than a kilometer to the national road, has also posed problems to residents. It has turned into a one-way street, as one side has become a parking lot for public utility jeepneys, cars and tricycles. Not only that. Informal settlers occupy both sides of a section of the road approaching the village gate just before the bridge over SLEx – an unwelcome sight that greets residents and visitors alike.

“It’s a struggle to drive to work,” said a project leader of the Information System Division of Insular Life in Filinvest City. (J. San Jose, personal communication, March 17, 2018). “One time one of the tires of my vehicle slid into a canal while I was trying to avoid tricycles parked on the road,” he said. Children who cross the road are another challenge to motorists.

For their part, Soldiers, Mutual Homes (1, 2 and 3), Camella Homes (2, 2D and 2E) and RCE subdivisions could be reached only via Soldiers Hill’s connecting road to the national highway, a traffic chokepoint. CARES became accessible to two other contiguous subdivisions to the south – Camella 1 and Greenheights, which are also

right beside SLEx to the west – with the construction of a gate and bridge on a creek at Block 35 of Soldiers. The gate opened in 2018.

Before CARES, the sole entry and exit point of both Camella 1 and Greenheights was a narrow road that crosses SLEx through a bridge and leads to the side of city hall on the congested national road.

Directive from the President

CARES came about because residents of Pleasant and other subdivisions and local government officials persisted to have it built to find relief from traffic congestion that was making their commute miserable.

Councilor Raul Corro principally authored the ordinance creating CARES in response to an executive order issued by then President Fidel Ramos for subdivision roads to be opened to motorists to help ease traffic congestion in Metro Manila. In 1993, the President directed mayors in Metro Manila to pass an ordinance requiring subdivision owners and developers to allow the use of their subdivision roads as “alternative routes.”

The President’s order came amid the traffic congestion along Edsa, and the then poorly maintained SLEx, which made a trip from Makati to Muntinlupa an hours-long agony. The problem on Edsa was partly addressed with the construction of tunnels and overpasses and C-5 as well as the adoption of number coding. The congestion on SLEx was addressed with the rehabilitation of the expressway and the construction of Skyway, which opened to traffic in stages in 1999, 2010 and 2011.

But these measures proved not to be enough because of the subsequent huge increase in the volume of motor vehicles in Metro Manila.

Caring for One Another

Corro (personal communication, July 16, 2018.), who drafted an ordinance and coined the word CARES, said the city had police powers under the Local Government Code to undertake CARES for the greater good.

Corro premised his ordinance on the fact that traffic congestion would fester if people did not care for one another and if they maintained a “not-in-my-backyard” attitude.

His second premise is the existence of only one national highway in the city despite a dramatic increase in population and the number of motor vehicles. In the ordinance, Corro placed the length of national, city and barangay roads then at only 40 km and the number of private and utility vehicles operating within Muntinlupa at the time between 450,000 and 500,000.

Figure 18. Campaign poster of Raul Corro, who topped the 2022 elections for councilors in District 2.

Photo by JVS

A study by the then Traffic, Environment and Discipline Office estimated the number of trips of all vehicles passing through the city and the southern corridor of Metro Manila at 2.2 million daily (Ordinance No. 02-045, 2002).

The Ramos presidency ended on June 30, 1998, but the city council approved Corro's proposed ordinance only on May 16, 2002. After the ordinance was approved, it would take more than a decade for the access road to be built and opened to traffic, even as traffic congestion worsened.

Long Road to CARES

CARES was first opened just before the elections in May 2013, but it was closed shortly after the polls following the defeat of then Mayor Aldrin San Pedro. The road reopened under Mayor Jaime Fresnedi in December 2014.

There were efforts as early as the late 1990s to set up an access road to Filinvest City from Pleasant. After Filinvest won the bidding for the development of the Alabang Stock Farm, it wanted to build a road to connect the former government property to Pleasant and Barangay Bayanan as part of its masterplan.

A vice president for finance of Filinvest approached PVHOA asking for a lot where a connecting road could be built. The PVHOA president suggested the lot across from his house near the guardhouse, but the Filinvest official proposed that the association find another location. The homeowners' association sought the help of Corro for an access road from Filinvest that would pass through across from Garcia's house onto Bautista Street in Bayanan. The owner of the lot in the area identified by Filinvest as a possible access road, however, could not be located.

Rejection

A top executive of Filinvest Land Inc. rejected the proposal at a meeting sometime in 1999 with then Mayor Jaime Fresnedi and Corro, contending that the city government had not even heeded Filinvest's request for fire trucks for high-rise

buildings and would now want an access road to Filinvest City. Filinvest Land expressed concern that the access road for all vehicles would result in traffic congestion in the CBD (Garcia, 2018). With the support of the city government, the PVHOA pressed on. It was able to convince three landowners to donate a portion of their land to the city sometime in 2002 and 2003 for a road to Filinvest on the expectation that the value of their properties would go up. One donor was enticed to take out a bank loan for the construction of the road on his property and his neighbors but failed to proceed with the construction because he lost the money in a casino (Garcia, 2018). PVHOA again approached Filinvest, which suggested that a road be built at the other end of the boundary between Filinvest Alabang and the subdivision.

When a new mayor, San Pedro, took office, Pleasant enlisted the help of Camella 2 residents and later those of Soldiers' Hills, Mutual Homes and RCE to form the lobby group SMCPR (Soldiers, Mutual, Camella, Pleasant and RCE). A landowner donated a lot for an access road to connect with a Filinvest road near the Research Institute for Tropical Medicine (RITM) after PVHOA persuaded him to do so with the assurance that the market price of his other properties in the village would double. The city accepted the donation and a contractor built the access road. But there was a hitch.

Mayor Takes Action

A wall separating the access road in Pleasant from a road in Filinvest City still stood in the way despite a city resolution calling for the roads to be connected. Feeling the pressure from SMCPR, which has a sizeable voting population, at a tense meeting in city hall, San Pedro, who was seeking reelection in 2013, took action and personally went to the site with police personnel. He kicked the wall in full view of a Filinvest

security officer, according to Garcia. “We were using police power,” said Corro. The wall was taken down and construction to link the roads began.

A Pleasant landowner donated parcels of land for the other end of CARES that would connect to Camella 2. The city government funded the road construction. CARES was finally opened to motorists a few weeks before the 2013 elections, earning the mayor brownie points. Motorists were able to use the access road without paying any fees.

Unpublished IRR and Suit

But CARES remaining open did not last. Soon after San Pedro lost the mayoralty in the election, Filinvest closed the road on the grounds that the implementing rules and regulations (IRR) of the ordinance establishing CARES had not been published (Corro, 2018). True enough, it was only on June 10, 2013, that the city council approved the IRR, or more than a decade after Ordinance No. 02-045 that created CARES and a task force to implement it was passed. The IRR, embodied in Ordinance No. 13-123, came out when San Pedro was still in office awaiting the turnover to his successor.

San Pedro and other city officials also faced a suit that officers of the Camella 2 homeowners association had filed in the Office of the Ombudsman calling for an end to the use of their subdivision road network (Camella Drive, Eagle Avenue, Canary, Hawk and Woodpecker). The president of Camella 2 HOA (R. Bautista, personal communication, October 30, 2018) maintained that the use of the roads by outsiders would make the subdivision vulnerable to burglaries and be subjected to noise from vehicular traffic. But “we just accommodated San Pedro during the elections [and allowed outsiders to use our roads for CARES],” he said.

The Office of the Ombudsman noted that lot titles in the subdivision had restrictions and that one cannot just open an entrance from another subdivision. A few weeks after a hearing on April 27, 2013, the Ombudsman ruled in favor of the Camella 2 HOA, affirming the latter's stand that its roads could not be part of CARES. The ruling led to the closure of the gate at Hawk Street (Bautista, 2018).

Pressing for Reopening

Despite the closure of CARES, SM CPR soldiered on, pushing for its reopening on the grounds that it would benefit the city and its residents. At one public hearing conducted by the city government, SM CPR officials stressed that CARES would lead to less traffic congestion along the national road and faster travel time not only for motorists but also for emergency vehicles.

In addition, the new route would reduce pollution from idling vehicles, especially those below the perennially congested Alabang viaduct (Garcia, 2018). They also pointed out that more vehicles going to Filinvest City would boost its income and the local economy and thus increase the city's tax revenue.

Pressed by SM CPR, the city council passed a resolution on Jan. 20, 2014, authorizing Fresnedi to enter into a memorandum of agreement (MOA) with Filinvest Alabang Inc. (FAI) "for the use of Lot 12, part of Filinvest City's road network, for passage of private residents" of SM CPR (Muntinlupa City Council, 2014). The resolution cited the advantages of CARES, including faster travel time and reduced traffic congestion along the national road as well as higher property values--among the benefits pointed out by SM CPR.

MOA, Access Road Reopens

Negotiations between the city government under Fresnedi and FAI resulted in the reopening of CARES in December 2014 under terms spelled out in an MOA that gave the company better control of the ingress and egress of vehicles. The MOA, among other things, authorized FAI to determine the number and class of vehicles that can use the access road and to issue stickers to vehicles at an initial cost of P500 each.

The agreement also allowed FAI sole control of the access gate and road on Lot 12, including the deployment of guards and placement of barriers and separators to maintain security and orderly traffic flow (Memorandum of Agreement between Filinvest Alabang Inc. and the City Government of Muntinlupa, 2014). FAI president Josephine G. Yap and Mayor Fresnedi signed the MOA on June 2, 2014.

With the link to Camella 2 closed after it won a complaint against the previous city administration, Fresnedi rehabilitated a barangay road between the subdivision and Camella 2D and part of Soldiers' Hills in 2014.

It was only on Dec. 5, 2017, that an ordinance ratifying the new IRR of Ordinance No. 02-045 was approved. With a signed MOU that addressed its concerns, FAI this time did not object to the late approval of the IRR.

Figure 19. Rehabilitated barangay road between Camella 2 and Camella 2D.

Photo by Allan Balila

Since its reopening, CARES stickers have been issued yearly to vehicles owned by residents of SM CPR. Government vehicles are allowed to use the access road even without stickers. Private motorcycles can use a portion of CARES until Pleasant so they can exit at Bautista Street toward the national road. They are barred from entering Filinvest City.

Use of the access road is limited to between 5 a.m. and 10 p.m. daily, a scheme that an appraiser (L. Modina, personal communication, October 12, 2018) of Hill Country Appraisal and Realty believed would weigh down further increases in land prices in Pleasant. Modina, who went with the author on an ocular visit to Pleasant and neighboring subdivisions, was on the BIR subcommittee that prepared the proposed eighth revision of zonal values for Muntinlupa that was implemented in July 2019.

Rise of CBD

Another government action that played a key role in the rapid urbanization of Muntinlupa and subsequent rise of property prices in Pleasant was the development of a vast tract of land in Alabang that became Filinvest City.

The Philippine government offered 244 hectares of mostly grazing land for joint development with the private sector to raise funds. Filinvest Corp. of Chinese-Filipino businessman Andrew Gotianun was chosen in 1991 by the Public Estates Authority (PEA) to be its partner in what was then billed as “the biggest joint-venture project of the government and the private sector” (Sarmiento, 1991). Filinvest bested Ayala Land Inc. and Robinson’s Land of the Gokongweis (Philippine Daily Inquirer, 1998) in a bidding to develop the prime property adjacent to Ayala Alabang Village and Alabang Town Center.

The government property had hosted the Serum and Vaccine Laboratory (SVL) of the Department of Health and a stock farm of the Department of Agriculture. The SVL produced anti-venom vaccine from venom extracted from cobras raised in an adjacent facility, while the stock farm bred cattle, goats and other livestock, and sold fresh milk to the public every morning (Bunye, 2016). Two other government facilities – the Food and Drug Administration and RITM – were also in the area. They still are. Part of the property on Alabang-Zapote Road had served as a venue for Big Bang Alabang, an amusement park hosting rides and slides during the Yuletide Season in the late '80s.

Controversial Bidding

The selection of Filinvest for the development of the Alabang property, however, was mired in controversy. Ayala Land questioned the award to Filinvest of the right to develop the property, prompting the administration of then President Corazon Aquino to form a three-member fact-finding committee led by then Philippine National Bank president Eduardo Espiritu. Malacañang rescinded the award following a recommendation from the committee that found that the selection process had been tainted with “irregularity and unfairness” (Cañares,1998).

Filinvest sued the government in December 1991 for nullifying the results (Philippine Daily Inquirer, 1998). A regional trial court (RTC) in Quezon City ruled on July 24, 1992, that the selection process was in order and that holding another bidding would be unfair to Filinvest and deprive it of its property right after it won the bidding.

The administration of newly elected President Ramos contested the RTC ruling in the Court of Appeals. But in 1993, the Office of the President turned around and decided to enter into a compromise agreement with Filinvest as part of government

efforts to attract investments and help pump-prime the economy. The appeals court affirmed the compromise deal on May 5, 1993, paving the way for Filinvest and the PEA to sign a joint-venture agreement on April 14, 1993.

Filinvest City

It was only in 1995 that Filinvest started developing the property into a mixed-used development. The PEA gave up its share in the joint venture in exchange for concessions from Filinvest. By 2012, the Gotianuns had sunk nearly P20 billion in Filinvest City (De la Fuente, 2012).

Today it is a CBD consisting of areas that host IT and BPO companies, hotels, serviced apartments, malls, supermarkets, hospitals, office and condominium buildings, a country club, a high-end residential area, a driving range, police and fire stations, transport hubs, a university and recently a central park. These areas are connected by tree-lined walkways and bike lanes. E-jeeps ply the central business district.

A report in 2016 quoting PLDT Inc. CEO Manuel V. Pangilinan that the company was considering establishing a campus-style headquarters in Filinvest City generated buzz and added to the attraction of Pleasant to potential investors. The transfer of PLDT headquarters, however, did not push through (Amojelar, 2016).

Three hospitals--Asian Hospital and Medical Center, Ospital ng Muntinlupa and RITM, and three hotels (Crimson, Acacia Manila and Bellevue) -- operate in Filinvest City. An upscale serviced apartment (Somerset Alabang Manila) has expanded the choices of tourists for accommodations in Filinvest City. One of the newest additions to Filinvest City is Far Eastern University (FEU) Alabang, which opened its campus to students in August 2018.

Filinvest City, a LEED-certified CBD, was hosting more than 40,000 people daily before the pandemic. Commercial lots in the CBD were for sale in the first quarter of 2018 at prices (excluding documentary stamp and transfer taxes) ranging from P162, 000 per sq. m. in the Palms District to P398, 000 per sq. m. in the Spectrum District (Arellano, 2018). At Palms Pointe, a seven-hectare subdivision in Filinvest City, about a kilometer away from Pleasant, lots were for sale at P70, 000 to P75, 000 per sq. m. in 2018 (OLX, 2018).

Chapter V

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

An environmental force – the opening of CARES – drove the surge in land prices in Pleasant. The road has enabled residents of several subdivisions to avoid being tied up in traffic on the national road and other thoroughfares in Muntinlupa, making the communities, particularly Pleasant, more accessible than before.

The alternative route has reduced not only travel time to work or business and to social, cultural and educational activities, but also stress associated with traffic congestion. It has even given residents of Pleasant access to the wide and green spaces of the CBD, where they can go walking, jogging, or biking—activities good for one’s physical and mental health. The CBD’s amenities have become positive externalities for Pleasant and its residents.

CARES has also made Pleasant one of the subdivisions in the city nearest the tollgates of SLEx and has linked it to other major roads, further making the village accessible. The access road also opened linkages to communities that offer residents of Pleasant opportunities, including employment.

The accessibility has made living in a neighborhood adjacent to a thriving CBD an attractive proposition, driving buyers to bid up the location.

Influence on Land Value

The findings of this case study support the proposition that improving accessibility with the construction of a transport infrastructure leads to higher values

of nearby properties. Clearly, CARES has been capitalized into land values in Pleasant.

The capitalization, estimated at P476 million in 2016, a bonanza for landowners in Pleasant, dwarfs the P39-million cost of building Phases 1 and 2 of the alternative route. The construction cost is about 10 percent of the capitalization.

The study also shows that proximity to a CBD, as posited by classic urban location theory, makes property values go up. But there was a catch. For decades land prices in Pleasant remained stagnant because being located beside a CBD did not provide the village quick access to the business district. A concrete fence separated Pleasant from the CBD.

Residents going to the CBD had to take a circuitous route that required passing through heavily congested areas -- the national road, the at-grade section of the Alabang viaduct and the Alabang public market. It was only after the fence was torn down, which resulted in unimpeded and direct access to the CBD via CARES, that the potential of Pleasant's real estate was unlocked: Land prices began their rapid ascent.

Generalization to Theoretical Propositions

The findings can thus be generalized to theoretical propositions about improved accessibility due to a road network such as CARES and proximity to a CBD raising values of land nearby. The access road and its capitalization came about because of other forces.

The political forces include the privatization of a large tract of land in Alabang that became a CBD, the directive from President Ramos requiring subdivisions to allow the use of their roads as alternative routes to help ease traffic congestion and the ordinance creating CARES. The development of the CBD and Muntinlupa, the

growing number of motor vehicles, the increase in population of the metropolis and neighboring provinces, and the rise of factories in these provinces are economic and social forces that contributed to traffic congestion.

The study also shows that creating alternative routes such as CARES is much cheaper than building new ones from scratch.

Recommendations

Land-Value Capture

The city government through the Assessor's Office can use capitalization to study the influence of new or improved transport infrastructures on land values in nearby communities and adjust real property taxes (RPT) accordingly.

The capitalization of CARES into the value of land around it has, in fact, given the city government an opportunity to raise funds to recover the infrastructure cost and finance other projects. City hall can increase RPT for landowners who benefit from the transport facility – a mechanism called “land-value capture” that aims to get a small share of the huge rise in the values of property.

RPT, Building Capacity

A comprehensive study of the capitalization of CARES covering properties on the city's tax map that saw their values go up due to the transport infrastructure could be undertaken and its findings used as a basis for raising RPT. This will entail building the capacity of the assessor's office to undertake the study. It's information system must also be upgraded to include the dates of the sale of properties and the amounts involved in the transactions to determine the infrastructure's influence on land values.

The dates and sales data can be taken from the DOAS that property owners submit to the assessor's office to get a tax declaration.

Levies

Levies could also be collected from businesses and motorists who benefited from lower transportation cost (travel time, fuel and vehicle maintenance). In fact, Pleasant, other subdivisions and FAI are already charging fees for the use of the access road through the issuance of stickers. Before the pandemic, Pleasant collected fees from employees and students who passed through its gate to the CBD. It still gets P100 from the fee that other subdivisions collect from motorists on top of the P500 charged by FAI.

FAI itself is reaping other benefits from CARES: The access road is increasing foot traffic to malls, retail outlets, restaurants, hotels and other commercial establishments in the CBD. Moreover, certain employees can report for work and students can go to school in the CBD without traffic congestion delay.

The city government, for its part, can get a share of the sticker fee but has so far not done so although it is tasked with the upkeep of the new route under the IRR of the ordinance creating CARES. Neither has it updated the schedule of market values (SMVs) to raise property taxes, a situation that makes more pressing the need to transfer the function of setting SMVs to a national agency from elected officials, who tend to balk at regularly updating property tax rates. Updating SMVs, especially for communities that benefit from CARES, could enable the local government to raise additional revenue and to finance other projects.

Valuation Tool Kit

Government agencies such as the BIR could also add the capitalization method to its tool kit in updating zonal values that it uses to levy the 6 percent capital gains tax on the sale, donation or inheritance of property. [Under Republic Act No. 12001, or the Real Property Valuation and Assessment Reform Act of 2024, however, the BIR can no longer determine the zonal value of land for internal revenue tax purposes and must use instead the schedule of market values that the Secretary of Finance approved.]

As for developers and other local governments contemplating a road like CARES, they can draw lessons from the lobbying efforts of subdivisions surrounding the alternative route, the ordinances on and IRR of the road, and the MOA between FAI and the city government in defining their roles in operating the access road.

REFERENCES

- Abadilla, E. V. (2021, April 13). SMC opens northbound section of Skyway Extension. *Manila Bulletin*. <https://mb.com.ph/2021/04/13/smc-opens-northbound-section-of-skyway-extension/>.
- Abiad, A., Farrin K., & Hale C. (2021). Sustaining transit investment in Asia's cities: A beneficiary-funding and land value perspective. Asian Development Bank. <https://www.adb.org/publications/sustaining-transit-investment-asia-cities>.
- Adkins, W. (1959). "Land Value Impacts of Expressways In Dallas, Houston and San Antonio, Texas." <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/LAND-VALUE-IMPACTS-OF-EXPRESSWAYS-IN-DALLAS%2C-AND-Adkins/ff885613429c8ba70ffbd266aafc9cd5bfdcc235#paper-header>.
- Ager, M. (2013, January 24). Palawan roads highest 'costing road' in PH—DPWH. *inquirer.net*. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/346265/palawan-roads-highest-costing-roads-in-ph-dpwh>.
- Alonso, W. (1964). Location and land use: toward a general theory of land rent. Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Mass.
- Amojelar, D. (2016, June 14). PLDT to build P10-B Alabang headquarters. *Manila Standard*. <http://manilastandard.net/business/208211/pldt-to-build-p10-b-alabang-headquarters.html>.
- Asian Development Bank Outlook (2019). Fostering Growth and Inclusion in Asia's Cities. <https://www.adb.org/publications/asian-development-outlook-2019-update>.
- Ayala Alabang Village Association (2019). <http://www.aava.com.ph>.
- Banzon, S. (2018, November 16). Now open: The completed Laguna Lake Highway, formerly known as C-6. <https://www.topgear.com.ph/news/motoring-news/laguna-lake-highway-opening-a2578-20181116>.
- Barr, M. (2022, February 8). The Long and Short of It: Lifespans of Paved Roadways. Ayres. <https://www.ayresassociates.com/the-long-and-short-of-it-lifespans-of-paved-roadways/>.
- Brown, F.A., & Michael, H. L. (1973). The Impact on Land Value of a Major Highway Interchange Near a Metropolitan Area. Joint Highway Research Project, Purdue University and Indiana State Highway Commission. <file:///C:/Users/Master/Downloads/Brown%20and%20Michael-The%20impact%20of%20land%20value%20on%20a%20major%20interchange%20near%20a%20metropolitan%20area.pdf>.
- Buensuceso, H. & Purisima, C. (2018). Funding infrastructure development in the Philippines: A roadmap toward land value capture. Milken Institute. <https://milkeninstitute.org/report/funding-transport-infrastructure-development-philippines-roadmap-toward-land-value-capture>.
- Buffington, J. (1967). A Study of the Impact of Interstate Highway 45 on Huntsville, Texas. Texas Transport Institute, Texas A&M University, College Station, Texas. <file:///C:/Users/Master/Downloads/Buffington->

%20Study%20of%20Impact%20of%20Interstate%20Highway%2045%20in%20Texas.pdf.

- Bunye, I. (2016, March 20). The Legacy of Andrew L. Gotianun Sr. *Sun Star Philippines*. <https://www.sunstar.com.ph/article/64409>.
- Camus, M. (2021, September 16). DOTr: Metro Manila Subway now 26 % complete. *Philippine Daily Inquirer*. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1488502/dotr-subway-construction-stuck-at-1-operational-by-2027-yet>.
- Cañares, C. (1998, March 27). FVR may be charged with plunder - Angara. *Philippine Daily Inquirer*.
- City Government of Muntinlupa (2022). Muntinlupa: A City that Cares. City of Muntinlupa Comprehensive Land Use Plan: 2016-2026.
- Cribbins, P.D., Hill, W.T. & Seagraves, H.O. (1962). Economic Impact of Selected Sections of Interstate Routes on Land Value and Use. Committee on Indirect Effects of Highway Improvements. <file:///C:/Users/Master/Downloads/Cribbins,%20Hill%20and%20Seagraves-Economic%20Impact%20of%20Selected%20Sections%20of%20Interstate%20Routes%20on%20Land%20Value%20and%20Use.pdf>.
- De Guzman, C. (2017, June 1). San Miguel Corp. fully opens Naia Expressway. *CNN Philippines*. <https://cnnphilippines.com/business/2017/06/01/San-Miguel-Corp-opens-NAIA-expressway.html>.
- De la Fuente, F. J. (2012, November 8). Filinvest Land rebrands project. *BusinessWorld*. <http://www.bworldonline.com/content.php?section=&title=Filinvest-Land-rebrands-flagship-project&id=61067>.
- Deuskar, D. & Zhang, Y. (2015, February 15). Mapping Manila's growth. *Philippine Daily Inquirer*.
- Ecological Profile of Muntinlupa (2016). Existing Land Use Profile, Part 3.
- Florida, R. (2017). The new urban crisis: Gentrification, housing bubbles, growing inequality and what we can do about it. London: Oneworld Publications.
- Gatzlaff, D. & Smith, M. (1993). The impact of the Miami Metrorail on the value of residencies near station locations. *Land Economics* 69 (1). 54-66. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/227638595_The_Impact_of_the_Miami_Metrorail_on_the_Value_of_Residences_Near_Station_Locations.
- Goldstein, S. (1963). Nonuser benefits from highways. US Bureau of Public Roads. <https://onlinepubs.trb.org/Onlinepubs/hrr/1963/20/20-009.pdf>.
- Gonzales-Navarro, M. & Quintana-Domeque, C. (2010). Public infrastructure, private investment and residential property values: Experimental evidence from street pavement. <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.175.2320&rep=rep1&type=pdf>.

- Haig, R. M. (1926). Toward an Understanding of the Metropolis. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 40(3), 402–434. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1885172>.
- Hou, Y. (2017). Traffic congestion, accessibility to employment, and housing prices: A study of single-family housing market in Los Angeles County. *Urban Studies*, 54(15), 3423–3445. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26428392>.
- Japan International Cooperation Agency (2017). Follow Up Survey on the Roadmap for Transport Infrastructure Development for Greater Capital Region. https://openjicareport.jica.go.jp/pdf/1000041638_01.pdf.
- Kivell, P. (1993). *Land use and the city*. London: Routledge.
- Lamudi (2018). <https://www.lamudi.com.ph/316sqm-lot-for-sale-in-palms-pointe-alabang.html>.
- Landis, J., Guhathakurta, S. & Zhang, M. (1994). Capitalization of Transit Investments into Single-Family Home Prices: A comparative Analysis of Five California Rail Transit Systems. University of California Transportation Center, University of California, Berkeley, CA. <http://escholarship.org/uc/item/80f3p5n1>.
- Langley, J. (1981). Highways and Property Values: The Washington Beltway Revisited. *Transportation Research Record* 812. <https://onlinepubs.trb.org/Onlinepubs/trr/1981/812/812-005.pdf>, 20.
- Lipset, S., Trow, M. & Coleman, J. (1956). *Union Democracy: The Internal Politics of the International Typographical Union*. Glencoe, Ill.: The Free Press.
- Manabat, J. (2021, April 22). Use of Skyway Stage 3 still free, SMC says to shoulder cost as long as it can. *ABS-CBN News*. <https://news.abs-cbn.com/business/04/22/21/no-toll-fee-skyway-stage-3-san-miguel-ramon-ang>.
- Memorandum of Agreement between Filinvest Alabang Inc. and the City Government of Muntinlupa. (2014).
- Mills, E. S. (1972). *Studies in the Structure of the Urban Economy*. Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Milman, O. (2021, February 9). ‘Invisible killer’: fossil fuels caused 8.7m deaths globally in 2018, research finds. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2021/feb/09/fossil-fuels-pollution-deaths-research>.
- Muntinlupa City Council Resolution No. 14-035 (2014). A Resolution Authorizing the City Mayor Hon. Atty. Jaime R. Fresnedi on Behalf of the City Government of Muntinlupa to Enter and Sign for the Memorandum of Agreement Between Filinvest Alabang Inc. for the Use of Lot 12 as Access Road for Passage of Private Residents of Pleasantville, Soldiers Hills Village, Mutual Homes Phase 1, 2 and 3, Camella Homes 2, 2D and 2E.
- Muth, R. (1969). *Cities and Housing*. Chicago, IL. University of Chicago Press.

- OLX (2018). <https://www.olx.ph/item/lots-for-sale-in-palms-pointe-muntinlupa-city-ID8H59k.html?h=e64541675f>.
- Ordinance No. 02-045 (2002). An Ordinance Establishing CARES by Interconnecting Subdivisions from Victoria Homes Subdivision to Filinvest Corporate City, Creating a Task Force to Implement the Same and for Other Purposes.
- Ordinance No. 17-124 (2017). An Ordinance Ratifying the New Implementing Rules and Regulations of Ordinance No. 02-045.
- Philippine Daily Inquirer (1998, March 28). Alabang deal legal—Filinvest.
- PhilStar Global (2019, July 30). What you need to know about the Makati Subway. <https://www.philstar.com/business/2019/07/30/1939231/what-you-need-know-about-makati-city-subway>.
- Railway Technology (2022, August 19). North-South Railway Project, Philippines. <https://www.railway-technology.com/projects/north-south-railway-project/>.
- Rey, A. (2021, Sept. 7). Cavite to be linked to C5 Link by Q4 202. *Rappler*. <https://www.rappler.com/business/connection-cavite-c5-link-q4-2022>.
- Sarmiento, J. V. (1991, July 16). Ayala, Robinsons, Filinvest shortlisted for Alabang venture. *Philippine Daily Inquirer*.
- Stuart, E. A., Huskamp, H. A., Duckworth, K., Simmons, J., Song, Z., Chernew, M., & Barry, C. L. (2014). Using propensity scores in difference-in-differences models to estimate the effects of a policy change. *Health services & outcomes research methodology*, 14(4), 166–182. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10742-014-0123-z>.
- Tabano, D. (2015, July 24). The new Muntinlupa-Cavite Expressway is now open. *Top Gear Philippines*. <https://www.topgear.com.ph/news/motoring-news/the-new-muntinlupa-cavite-expressway-is-now-open>.
- Traffic Engineering Division of the Muntinlupa Traffic Management Bureau (2017). City Alternative Route Entry and Exit Systems (CARES) Traffic Impact Study.
- Yin, R. K. (2003). *Case study research: Design and Methods* (3rd ed.), Sage Publications.
- World Bank (2015). *East Asia's Changing Urban Landscape: Measuring a Decade of Spatial Growth*. Urban Development Series.
- Zhao, Z. & Levinson, D. (2012). Introduction to the special issue on value capture for transportation finance. *Journal of Transport and Land Use* 5 (1), 1-3.

Appendices

APPENDIX A

Guards as Real Estate Agents

By Juan V. Sarmiento Jr.

Security guards and a member of the maintenance crew have joined officers and staff of the homeowners association in becoming real estate agents on the side in Pleasant.

They enjoy an advantage over agents from outside the subdivision because they know the owners and location of the land for sale – information not readily available to the public as properties for sale in Pleasant are hardly posted on the internet, advertised on classified ads of newspapers, or marked with a sale sign.

Take the case of Joseph, who has served for two decades as volunteer guard of Pleasant.

He claimed to be instrumental in selling as of 2018 five parcels of land, two of which took place in 2015, his last year of employment in the subdivision.

Joseph said he could have sold seven lots but two were appropriated by other agents who cut him off the deal.

He attributed his ability to sell land to his work as volunteer guard, which enabled him to get to know many lot owners and caretakers.

“As a guard, I ask those who pass the gate if they’re lot owners. Then I get their contact numbers,” he said.

When a visitor asks him at the guardhouse for any lots for sale, he would link the prospective buyer or his agent to a landowner who wants to sell. He gets a commission from closed sales.

Another volunteer guard, Christian, became an agent in 2014 when the market

was starting to heat up. He was able to facilitate the sale of a 326-sqm lot on Holiday Inn Street, for which he was given a referral fee of P20, 000, an amount that he said he used to buy a motorcycle.

The referral fee was more than double the monthly pay of Christian, who worked at the village for close to six years until January 2018.

Erwin also dabbled in real estate business while working as a maintenance worker.

He partnered with the HOA secretary, a former subdivision “caretaker” and a family friend of the sellers for the sale of two lots – 297 sq. m. and 325 sq. m. on Regent Street – in May 2018.

The two lots, sold for P20, 000 per sq. m., were among the parcels of land that Erwin was able to help sell in the village over the past few years.

One sale he serendipitously facilitated was in 2016. One morning he asked a visitor inquiring at the PVHOA office about unpaid association dues of a property on Peninsula Avenue whether he was looking for a lot. He said a lot was newly available for sale.

When the visitor expressed interest in the lot, Erwin promptly took him on his motorbike to the residence of an officer of the homeowners’ association, who was acting as an agent.

After the meeting between the visitor and the officer was done, he took the former to the lot for ocular inspection. Days later, the sale was closed.

APPENDIX B

Near Workplace, Rental Business

By Juan V. Sarmiento Jr.

One driver of demand for property in Pleasant is its being adjacent to Filinvest City.

For those who have the means, buying land is the key to living near the workplace. Among such buyers are a couple, both physicians at Ospital ng Muntinlupa, a city-run medical facility right beside Asian Hospital in Filinvest City.

The couple are staying at the residence of their parents in San Jose Village on Alabang-Zapote Road, just across from the Ayala Town Center. “They want to build a house in Pleasant, which they find attractive,” said Danny Garcia, president of PVHOA.

For landowners and investors proximity to Filinvest City is an opportunity to cater to the huge housing needs of people working and studying in the CBD.

James Ledesma and his sister sold two houses and the 227-sq. m. lot on which the improvements sit for P6.8 million in July 2018 to a dermatologist at the Research Institute for Tropical Medicine (RITM), who has clinics in other parts of the metropolis. The dermatologist remodeled the improvements so he could rent them out to doctors and students.

RITM and Far Eastern University Alabang are just 200 to 300 meters away from the dermatologist’s property on Mandarin Avenue and are right next to the CARES gate of Filinvest City and Pleasant.

Providing lodging to employees and students is also the reason Mariano Notorio put up a three-story building on a 300-sq. m. lot on Mandarin Avenue, a stone's throw from the CARES gate and Far Eastern University Alabang.

The PVHOA approved in the last quarter of 2018 Notorio's application to construct the building, which was finished in 2021.

Others are also into rental business.

A couple, now working in the United States, acquired a 530-sq. m. property at the corner of Regent and Hyatt Streets, and put up four up-and-down houses in 2017, three of which are for rent. One is to be used by the owners when they are on their visit to the country. Two units on Regent are being rented out in 2018 for P15,000 a month and the third unit, a bigger one, goes for P18,000 a month.

Other lot owners in Pleasant are into leasing before these new apartments were built, responding to demand for housing.

Perseus Calvario, who worked in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia from 1996 to 2000 as a welder, is renting out a four-door apartment that he built on a 300-sq. m. lot he acquired on Regent Avenue shortly after CARES opened. Each up-and-down unit has a floor area of 60 sq. m. It has two rooms and two toilets and baths, and was leased in 2018 for P10,000 a month, which Calvario said was cheaper than the unit with two rooms beside his residence on Mandarin Avenue that was offered for P16,000 a month.

One of Calvario's tenants is employed at RITM, a short walk from the apartment. Walking to get to work saves the tenant time. He and his family used to live in Biñan, Laguna. Their child goes to school at the Muntinlupa School for Child Development, now called the Master's School, some 300 meters from the apartment.

Among the biggest apartments in the village are those on Peninsula Avenue,

owned by two Argana brothers. Two three-story Argana Apartments each have 15 units for rent.

Townhouses

Even before CARES was built some businessmen had taken the city government plan as a cue to construct housing units in Pleasant.

FNB Construction Supply put up three townhouses on Mandarin Avenue in 2010 on reports that the opening of CARES was imminent. Each unit – lot area of 100 sq. m., floor area of 130 sq. m., three rooms, two toilets and baths and a parking slot – sold for P3.5 million.

In 2015, shortly after CARES was reopened, the Barrions built two townhouses on the corner of Regent and Hyatt that his group had bought for P8, 000 per sq. m. One unit (lot area of 100 sq. m., floor area of 150 sq. m., three rooms, two toilets and baths, and a parking slot) was sold for P5.5 million. “But selling it was not easy because it is ‘high-end’ and pricewise it is bigger than the first townhouses we built,” said Ferdinand Niño M. Barrion, general manager of FNB Construction Supply. The second unit was being rented out in 2018 for P20, 000 a month.

Barrion said the company no longer builds townhouses in Pleasant because land prices have gone up. “We stopped buying land in Pleasant when the price hit P10, 000 per sq. m.” FNB Construction has instead moved to other areas where land is not as expensive as that in Pleasant.

Leasing business is not new in Pleasant. The first set of apartments in Pleasant was put up by the owners of the subdivision on Mandarin Avenue. The Buenaventuras built 31 apartment units in the late 1980s. Five were rent-to-own. “In the near future, the [heirs of the developer] would tear down the small apartments,” said PVHOA

president Danny Garcia. “In the meantime, they need to earn from rentals to pay for taxes. But they are losing on the cost of money. That’s why they are not fixing the apartments and are not renewing leases.”

Other businesses, such as warehousing, holding of events, and car supply and maintenance, have sprung up after the access road opened to traffic.

APPENDIX C

Land Transactions in Pleasant, South Greenheights
and Lakeview from 2009 to 2021 Based on Records
of the City Assessor's Office of Muntinlupa

1. PLEASANT (Test group)

SEQUENCE# DEC. DATE LOCATION KIND CLASSIF. AREA

2009

TR 02875 2/19/2009 PLEASANT Land R 110 sq. m.
TR 02876 2/19/2009 PLEASANT Land R 110
TR 02877 2/19/2009 PLEASANT Land R 110
TR 02889 12/4/2009 RD LOT 1 PLEASANT Land R 351
TR 02893 5/14/2009 PLEASANT Land R 322
TR 02912 5/20/2009 MANDARIN AVE. COR REGENT ST. Land R 451

2010

TR 02911 12/10/2010 INTERCON ST. Land R 300
TR 02890 8/31/2010 PLEASANT Land R 300
TR 02887 12/23/2010 PENINSULA COR HYATT STS. Land R 358
TR 02883 5/24/2010 PENINSULA ST. Land R 300
TR 02930 8/18/2010 PLEASANT Land R 299

2011

TR 02882 9/20/2011 PLEASANT Land R 300
TR 02885 3/17/2011 PENSULA ST. Land R 150
TR 02888 8/26/2011 INTERCON ST. Land R 300

2012

TR 01886 5/7/2012 PENINSULA ST. Land R 300
TR 01887 5/7/2012 PENINSULA ST. Land R 300
TR 01875 5/7/2012 PLEASANT Land R 307
TR 01709 6/11/2012 PLEASANT Land R 304
TR 01711 1/26/2012 PLEASANT Land R 300
TR 01691 9/27/2012 REGENT ST. Land R 140
TR 01692 10/5/2012 MANDARIN AVE. Land R 160
TR 01693 11/6/2012 REGENT ST. Land R 113
TR 01694 10/19/2012 REGENT ST. Land R 80

TR 01664 6/29/2012 HYATT ST. Land R 150
TR 01665 2/2/2012 HYATT ST. Land R 150
TR 01666 7/31/2012 HYATT ST. Land R 150
TR 01667 5/21/2012 HYATT ST. Land R 150
TR 01650 8/30/2012 MANDARIN AVE. Land R 273

2013

TR 01872 5/21/2013 REGENT ST. Land R 405
TR 01636 5/30/2013 MANDARIN Land R 311
TR 01637 5/30/2013 MANDARIN Land R 339
TR 01638 5/30/2013 MANDARIN Land R 260
TR 01639 5/30/2013 MANDARIN Land R 265
TR 01640 5/30/2013 MANDARIN Land R 265
TR 01641 5/30/2013 MANDARIN Land R 241
TR 01642 5/30/2013 MANDARIN Land R 295
TR 01643 5/30/2013 MANDARIN Land R 313
TR 01647 5/22/2013 MANDARIN Land R 282
TR 01648 5/22/2013 MANDARIN Land R 295
TR 01649 5/22/2013 MANDARIN Land R 288
TR 01661 4/26/2013 HYATT ST. Land R 300

2014

TR 01718 1/2/2014 PENINSULA ST. Land R 300
TR 01719 1/2/2014 PENINSULA ST. Land R 300
TR 01720 1/2/2014 PENINSULA ST. Land R 300
TR 01743 2/6/2014 REGENT ST. Land R 300
TR 01716 7/14/2014 PENINSULA ST. Land R 300
TR 01717 7/14/2014 PENINSULA ST. Land R 300
TR 01888 9/23/2014 MANDARIN COR. PENINSULA Land R 419
TR 01884 9/11/2014 PENINSULA ST. Land R 300
TR 01710 4/23/2014 PENINSULA ST. Land R 150
TR 01689 11/10/2014 PENINSULA ST. Land R 300
TR 01671 1/30/2014 HYATT ST. Land R 300
TR 01568 5/23/2014 MANDARIN Land R 300
TR 01644 1/23/2014 MANDARIN Land R 280
TR 01645 1/23/2014 MANDARIN Land R 274
TR 01646 1/23/2014 MANDARIN Land R 289

2015

TR 01904 4/1/2015 PENINSULA ST. Land R 299
TR 01703 10/15/2015 PENINSULA ST. Land R 305
TR 01715 2/23/2015 REGENT ST. Land R 300

2016

TR 01749 3/28/2016 HOLIDAY INN ST. Land R 293
TR 01744 5/18/2016 PENINSULA ST. Land R 300
TR 01735 7/11/2016 REGENT ST. Land R 333
TR 01736 7/11/2016 REGENT ST. Land R 202
TR 01737 7/4/2016 REGENT ST. Land R 300
TR 01897 10/20/2016 MANDARIN Land R 286
TR 01898 10/27/2016 MANDARIN Land R 270
TR 01899 10/27/2016 MANDARIN Land R 275
TR 01900 10/27/2016 MANDARIN Land R 287
TR 01901 10/27/2016 MANDARIN Land R 344
TR 01902 10/27/2016 MANDARIN Land R 414
TR 01903 10/27/2016 MANDARIN Land R 616

TR 01652 9/1/2016 MANDARIN Land R 313
TR 01653 5/18/2016 INTERCON ST. Land R 300
TR 01654 9/1/2016 MANDARIN Land R 300
TR 01655 9/1/2016 MANDARIN Land R 300
TR 01660 10/13/2016 MANDARIN Land R 300
TR 01730 5/31/2016 INTERCON COR. REGENT Land R 455
TR 01731 5/11/2016 HYATT COR. REGENT Land R 530
TR 01733 7/11/2016 REGENT ST. Land R 333

2017

TR 01885 3/14/2017 PENINSULA ST. Land R 300
TR 01734 4/3/2017 REGENT ST. Land R 333
TR 01746 9/13/2017 PENINSULA ST. Land R 300
TR 01738 10/12/2017 REGENT ST. Land R 300
TR 01739 10/12/2017 REGENT ST. Land R 300
TR 01740 10/12/2017 REGENT ST. Land R 297
TR 01876 10/12/2017 REGENT ST. Land R 300
TR 01877 10/12/2017 REGENT ST. Land R 300
TR 01878 10/12/2017 REGENT ST., Land R 300
TR 01879 10/12/2017 REGENT ST. Land R 300
TR 01794 8/29/2017 INTERCON ST. Land R 300
TR 01729 2/3/2017 INTERCON ST. Land R 300
TR 01724 11/23/2017 HYATT COR. INTERCON Land R 507
TR 01672 11/22/2017 REGENT ST. Land R 147
TR 01686 9/13/2017 PENINSULA ST. Land R 326
TR 01569 6/1/2017 MANDARIN Land R 313
TR 01570 6/1/2017 MANDARIN Land R 309
TR 01662 5/9/2017 HYATT ST. Land R 300

2018

TR 01745 2/20/2018 PENINSULA ST. Land R 300
TR 01747 2/20/2018 PENINSULA ST. Land R 313
TR 01748 2/20/2018 PENINSULA ST. Land R 300
TR 01732 3/22/2018 REGENT ST. Land R 785
TR 01797 5/11/2018 INTERCON ST. Land R 475
TR 01795 5/2/2018 MANDARIN ST. Land R 300
TR 01741 10/1/2018 REGENT ST. Land R 325
TR 01742 10/1/2018 REGENT ST. Land R 336
TR 01755 11/28/2018 PENINSULA ST. Land R 299
TR 01753 11/28/2018 PENINSULA ST. Land R 290
TR 01690 4/13/2018 REGENT ST. Land R 158
TR 01663 1/25/2018 HYATT COR. INTERCON Land R 360
TR 01656 4/4/2018 INTERCON ST. Land R 93

2019

TR 01798 1/31/2019 REGENT ST. Land R 221
TR 01754 9/30/2019 PENINSULA ST. Land R 305
TR 01751 4/24/2019 PENINSULA ST. Land R 321
TR 01712 10/14/2019 REGENT ST. Land R 300
TR 01713 10/14/2019 REGENT ST. Land R 300

TR 01714 10/14/2019 REGENT ST. Land R 300
TR 01696 10/24/2019 PENINSULA ST. Land R 300
TR 01697 12/5/2019 PENINSULA ST. Land R 309
TR 01687 9/2/2019 PENINSULA ST. Land R 336
TR 01688 9/2/2019 PENINSULA ST. Land R 312
TR 01668 4/15/2019 HYATT ST. Land R 100

2020

TR 01796 10/26/2020 MANDARIN Land R 300
TR 01752 9/28/2020 PENINSULA ST. Land R 306
TR 01695 9/28/2020 PENINSULA ST. Land R 300
TR 01700 12/3/2020 HYATT ST. Land R 330

2021

TR 01704 3/15/2021 HOLIDAY INN ST. Land R 300
TR 01705 4/19/2021 HOLIDAY INN ST. Land R 300
TR 01698 5/10/2021 HOLIDAY INN ST. Land R 300
TR 01699 5/10/2021 HOLIDAY INN ST. Land R 300
TR 01721 6/1/2021 PENINSULA ST. Land R 300
TR 01708 8/10/2021 HOLIDAY INN ST. Land R 294
TR 01880 4/15/2021 PENINSULA ST. Land R 300
TR 01881 4/15/2021 PENINSULA ST. Land R 300
TR 01750 8/2/2021 HOLIDAY INN ST. Land R 293
TR 01685 4/19/2021 MANDARIN Land R 300
TR 01651 6/8/2021 INTERCON ST. Land R 300

2. SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS (Test group)

SEQUENCE # DEC. DATE LOCATION KIND CLASSIF. AREA

2009

TR 02704 7/31/2009 SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS Land R 240 sq. m.
TR 02708 11/5/2009 QUERCUS ST. Land R 240
TR 02720 5/27/2009 XYLOMELUM ST. Land R 219.50
TR 02721 1/9/2009 ORCHIDS ST. Land R 303
TR 02727 2/19/2009 PRIMROSE ST. Land R 240
TR 02735 2/6/2009 ROSEMARY ST. Land R 240
TR 02736 1/20/2009 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA AVE. Land R 635
TR 02739 8/14/2009 S ALVENDIA COR RD L5 Land R 438
TR 02740 6/15/2009 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA AVE Land R 775
TR 02744 2/19/2009 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA ST. Land R 325
TR 02758 12/9/2009 GARDENIA COR VERBENA ST. Land R 313
TR 02769 9/24/2009 SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS Land R 240
TR 02773 7/21/2009 VERBENA ST. Land R 240
TR 02776 4/28/2009 SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS Land R 300
TR 02798 3/23/2009 PRIMROSE ST. Land R 240
TR 02803 11/10/2009 QUERCUS COR S ALVENDIA AVE. Land R 355
TR 02805 2/20/2009 ROSEMARY ST. Land R 240
TR 02808 6/2/2009 ROSEMARY ST. Land R 240

TR 02817 6/11/2009 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA AVE. Land R 66
TR 02846 10/15/2009 SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS Land R 179

2010

TR 01565 2/10/2020 WINTERGREEN ST. Land R 63
TR 02703 1/29/2010 ZINNIA ST. Land R 240
TR 02709 7/19/2010 QUERCUS ST. Land R 240
TR 02722 1/20/2010 ORCHID ST. Land R 292
TR 02725 7/16/2010 PRIMROSE ST. Land R 276
TR 02726 2/8/2010 PRIMEROSE ST. Land R 240
TR 02728 12/22/2010 QUERCUS ST. Land R 240
TR 02779 5/6/2010 HYACINTH ST. Land R 150
TR 02780 4/26/2010 HYACINTH ST. Land R 160.50
TR 02781 3/24/2010 LAVENDER ST. Land R 300
TR 02801 3/17/2010 PRIMROSE COR S ALVENDIA AVE. Land R 355
TR 02804 7/5/2010 SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS Land R 240
TR 02813 6/24/2010 COR JASMIN ST. Land R 321
TR 02818 3/24/2010 SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS Land R 80
TR 02819 2/2/2011 SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS Land R 300
TR 02830 11/26/2010 SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS Land R 359
TR 02838 12/29/2010 SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS Land R 300
TR 02839 8/31/2010 WINTERGREEN ST. Land R 300
TR 02847 8/2/2010 WINTERGREEN ST. Land R 360
TR 02848 11/12/2010 WINTERGREEN ST. Land R 360
TR 02849 8/2/2010 WINTERGREEN ST. Land R 180

2011

TR 02707 12/29/2011 QUERCUS COR ZINNIA Land R 374
TR 02714 11/17/2011 ZINNIA ST. Land R 350
TR 02717 11/17/2011 ZINNIA ST. Land R 350
TR 02718 10/5/2011 ORCHIDS ST. Land R 356
TR 02719 4/20/2011 ORCHIDS ST. Land R 311
TR 02741 12/6/2011 NEAR SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS Land R 2,050
TR 02745 12/6/2011 NEAR SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS Land R 5,349
TR 02746 2/10/2011 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA AVE. Land R 194
TR 02747 4/6/2011 SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS Land R 213
TR 02748 11/9/2011 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA AVE. Land R 88
TR 02757 2/23/2011 FLEURDELIZ ST. Land R 196
TR 02761 8/4/2011 HYACINTH ST. Land R 99
TR 02762 8/16/2011 HYACINTH ST. Land R 141
TR 02772 10/5/2011 VERBENA ST. Land R 240
TR 02806 11/17/2011 ROSEMARY ST. Land R 240
TR 02809 4/4/2011 COR SOLIVEN ALVENDIA Land R 358
TR 02811 1/31/2011 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA Land R 300
TR 02814 1/10/2011 EVERLASTING CIRCLE Land R 300

2012

TR 01182 3/27/2012 QUERCUS ST. Land R 240
TR 01192 11/27/2012 QUERCUS ST. Land R 240
TR 01252 1/27/2012 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA AVE. Land R 85

TR 01278 2/10/2012 EVERLASTING CIRCLE Land R 83
TR 01364 12/20/2012 SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS Land R 300
TR 01385 7/23/2012 NARCISSUS ST. Land R 300
TR 01387 8/14/2012 NARCISSUS ST. Land R 300
TR 01418 9/4/2012 PRIMROSE ST. Land R 240
TR 01429 7/3/2012 QUERCUS ST. Land R 240
TR 01444 3/15/2012 ROSEMARY ST. Land R 240
TR 01457 9/17/2012 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA ST. Land R 300
TR 01463 10/25/2012 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA ST. Land R 300
TR 01540 5/24/2012 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA Land R 337

2013

TR 01100 5/28/2013 ZINNIA ST. Land R 240
TR 01126 6/20/2013 QUERCUS ST. Land R 240
TR 01127 12/10/2013 QUERCUS ST. Land R 120
TR 01124 10/21/2013 SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS Land R 240
TR 01144 12/12/2013 SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS Land R 210
TR 01185 1/29/2013 QUERCUS ST. Land R 240
TR 01211 7/30/2013 MORNING GLORY ST. Land R 278
TR 01219 1/21/2013 CAMELLA ST. Land R 300
TR 01243 1/30/2013 SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS Land R 336
TR 01268 12/27/2013 TULIP COR. SUNFLOWER STS. Land R 535
TR 01304 11/26/2013 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA AVE. Land R 396
TR 01322 12/5/2013 VERBENA ST. Land R 240
TR 01358 9/6/2013 EVERLASTING ST. and R 300
TR 01361 11/29/2013 EVERLASTING CIRCLE Land R 300
TR 01427 1/4/2013 XYLOMELUM ST. Land R 356
TR 01407 8/6/2013 ORCHIDS ST. Land R 140
TR 01412 5/10/2013 ORCHIDS ST. Land R 120
TR 01413 5/3/2013 ORCHIDS ST. Land R 120
TR 01455 6/4/2013 SOLIVEN-ALVENDIA AVE. Land R 300
TR 01456 12/4/2013 SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS Land R 300
TR 01468 8/23/2013 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA ST. Land R 300
TR 01510 12/26/2013 EVERLASTING CIRCLE Land R 414
TR 01531 12/26/2013 EVERLASTING CIRCLE Land R 210

2014

TR 01104 4/1/2014 ROSEMARY ST. Land R 240
TR 01152 5/29/2014 SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS Land R 477
TR 01209 4/8/2014 ROSEMARY ST. Land R 240
TR 01256 4/16/2014 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA EXT. Land R 350
TR 01267 10/22/2014 SUNFLOWER ST. COR. TULIP ST. Land R 403
TR 01281 9/29/2014 FLEURDELIZ ST. Land R 301
TR 01258 6/27/2014 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA ST. Land R 69
TR 01300 3/7/2014 GARDENIA ST. Land R 298
TR 01303 10/16/2014 GARDENIA ST. Land R 275
TR 01317 1/15/2014 HYACINTH ST. Land R 240
TR 01327 2/12/2014 VERBENA ST. Land R 240
TR 01337 2/3/2014 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA ST. Land R 300
TR 01352 1/2/2014 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA AVE. Land R 300

TR 01405 11/18/2014 NARCISSUS ST. Land R 120
TR 01423 2/14/2014 PRIMROSE ST. Land R 240
TR 01440 10/3/2014 QUERCUS ST. Land R 240
TR 01477 1/28/2014 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA AVE. Land R 300

2015

TR 01106 12/28/2015 ROSEMARY ST. Land R 240
TR 01166 9/1/2015 PRIMROSE ST. Land R 287
TR 01189 7/23/2015 QUERCUS ST. Land R 240
TR 01200 3/19/2015 ROSEMARY COR. XYLOMELUM Land R 333
TR 01259 4/20/2015 SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS, Land R 73
TR 01260 5/13/2015 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA ST. Land R 73
TR 01273 10/23/2015 TULIP ST. Land R 68.50
TR 01274 10/23/2015 TULIP ST. Land R 43.50
TR 01277 11/4/2015 EVERLASTING CIRCLE Land R 120
TR 01279 2/6/2015 EVERLASTING CIRCLE Land R 83
TR 01289 10/28/2015 FLEUR DE LIZ ST. Land R 135
TR 01431 5/11/2015 QUERCUS ST. Land R 240
TR 01433 9/29/2015 QUERCUS ST. Land R 240
TR 01450 7/31/2015 ROSEMARY ST. Land R 120
TR 01467 2/24/2015 SOLIVEN-ALVENDIA ST. Land R 300
TR 01471 2/20/2015 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA AVE. Land R 300
TR 01509 12/28/2015 EVERLASTING CIRCLE Land R 150
TR 01525 8/10/2015 EVERLASTING CIRCLE Land R 359
TR 1557 5/7/2015 WINTERGREEN ST. Land R 360

2016

TR 01123 1/26/2016 QUERCUS ST. Land R 120
TR 01101 3/7/2016 ZINNIA ST. Land R 120
TR 01102 6/3/2016 ZINNIA ST. Land R 169
TR 01135 6/24/2016 PRIMROSE ST. Land R 240
TR 01153 4/25/2016 ORCHID ST. Land R 432
TR 01157 1/18/2016 ORCHID ST. Land R 312
TR 01167 12/2/2016 PRIMROSE ST. Land R 258
TR 01190 8/23/2016 QUERCUS ST., Land R 240
TR 01205 9/1/2016 YELLOW BELL ST. Land R 165
TR 01206 3/14/2016 ROSEMARY COR. YELLOW BELL Land R 168
TR 01207 6/2/2016 ROSEMARY ST. Land R 240
TR 01210 1/21/2016 ROSEMARY ST. Land R 240
TR 01231 6/30/2016 SUNFLOWER ST. Land R 300
TR 01255 7/15/2016 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA AVE. Land R 365
TR 01275 10/20/2016 EVERLASTING CIRCLE Land R 73
TR 01251 8/1/2016 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA ST. Land R 468
TR 01307 7/19/2016 VERBENA ST. Land R 240
TR 01314 9/23/2016 HYACINTH ST. Land R 270
TR 01338 3/11/2016 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA ST. Land R 300
TR 01342 1/21/2016 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA Land R 300
TR 01353 9/9/2016 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA COR. JASMINE Land R 321
TR 01422 3/15/2016 PRIMROSE ST. Land R 240
TR 01451 5/4/2016 ROSEMARY ST. Land R 120

TR 01452 5/19/2016 ROSEMARY ST. Land R 120
TR 01474 5/24/2016 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA AVE. Land R 300
TR 01508 7/26/2016 EVERLASTING CIRCLE Land R 150
TR 01553 10/5/2016 WINTERGREEN ST. Land R 360

2017

TR 01109 2/16/2017 ROSEMARY ST. Land R 240
TR 01116 5/3/2017 ROSEMARY ST. Land R 240
TR 01136 4/21/2017 PRIMROSE ST. Land R 120
TR 01138 9/18/2017 PRIMROSE ST. Land R 90
TR 01139 7/21/2017 PRIMROSE ST. Land R 90
TR 01165 1/11/2017 PRIMROSE ST. Land R 291
TR 01168 2/17/2017 PRIMROSE ST. Land R 247
TR 01199 4/20/2017 ROSEMARY ST. Land R 240
TR 01216 11/28/2017 XYLOMELUM ST. Land R 160
TR 01222 10/23/2017 SUNFLOWER ST. Land R 300
TR 01241 11/27/2017 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA AVENUE EXT. Land R 381
TR 01292 3/13/2017 FLEURDELIZ ST. Land R 361
TR 01299 12/18/2017 GARDENIA ST. Land R 298
TR 01404 8/17/2015 NARCISSUS ST. Land R 120
TR 01376 4/21/2017 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA Land R 108
TR 01377 5/15/2017 MORNING GLORY ST. Land R 150
TR 01378 12/13/2017 MORNING GLORY ST. Land R 150
TR 01386 12/21/2017 NARCISSUS STREET Land R 300
TR 01390 5/18/2017 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA AVE. Land R 126
TR 01391 6/19/2017 NARCISSUS STREET Land R 150
TR 01399 4/21/2017 S. ALVENDIA COR NARCISSUS ST. Land R 355
TR 01476 9/22/2017 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA AVE. Land R 300
TR 01532 1/23/2017 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA AVE. Land R 396
TR 01544 8/30/2017 ROSEMARY COR WINTER GREEN Land R 358
TR 01554 9/19/2017 WINTERGREEN ST. Land R 360

2018

TR 01095 3/2/2018 ZINNIA ST. Land R 240
TR 01097 12/10/2018 ZINNIA ST. Land R 240
TR 01098 4/2/2018 ZINNIA COR. PRIMROSE STS. Land R 356
TR 01119 2/7/2018 QUERCUS ST. Land R 240
TR 01125 4/27/2018 QUERCUS ST. Land R 240
TR 01137 2/15/2018 YELLOW BELL ST. Land R 100
TR 01105 2/2/2018 ROSEMARY ST. Land R 240
TR 01107 7/18/2018 ROSEMARY ST. Land R 240
TR 01169 1/16/2018 XYLOMELUM COR. PRIMROSE STS. Land R 337
TR 01181 9/12/2018 QUERCUS ST. Land R 240
TR 01191 6/21/2018 QUERCUS ST. Land R 240
TR 01186 1/15/2018 QUERCUS ST. Land R 42
TR 01187 1/15/2018 QUERCUS COR XYLOMELUM Land R 200
TR 01188 1/15/2018 XYLOMELUM ST. Land R 91
TR 01193 12/20/2018 QUERCUS COR. XYLOMELUM Land R 332
TR 01194 4/3/2018 QUERCUS ST. Land R 120
TR 01227 6/21/2018 FLEUR DE LIZ ST. Land R 308

TR 01228 9/18/2018 FLEURDELIZ ST. Land R 355
TR 01250 9/28/2018 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA AVE. Land R 370
TR 01375 1/24/2018 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA Land R 126
TR 01280 5/29/2018 SUNFLOWER ST. Land R 375
TR 01283 4/10/2018 EVERLASTING CIRCLE Land R 274
TR 01284 8/10/2018 FLEURDELIZ ST. Land R 270
TR 01285 4/3/2018 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA Land R 396
TR 01290 4/5/2018 GARDENIA ST. Land R 280
TR 01333 8/28/2018 VERBENA ST. Land R 240
TR 01354 3/15/2018 JASMINE ST. Land R 200
TR 01351 5/3/2018 SOLIVEN-ALVENDIA AVE. Land R 300
TR 01357 9/17/2018 EVERLASTING ST. Land R 300
TR 01362 10/8/2018 LAVENDER ST. Land R 170
TR 01363 12/4/2018 LAVENDER ST. Land R 130
TR 01389 3/8/2018 NARCISSUS ST. Land R 108
TR 01379 4/23/2018 MORNING GLORY ST. Land R 100
TR 01380 4/23/2018 MORNING GLORY COR. S. ALVENDIA Land R 111
TR 01395 2/2/2018 NARCISSUS ST. Land R 240
TR 01403 9/13/2018 NARCISSUS ST. Land R 120
TR 01432 5/15/2018 QUERCUS ST. Land R 240
TR 01436 9/3/2018 QUERCUS ST. Land R 240
TR 01475 1/3/2018 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA Land R 300
TR 01481 4/17/2018 EVERLASTING CIRCLE and R 300
TR 01482 6/25/2018 EVERLASTING CIRCLE and R 300
TR 01489 6/1/2018 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA AVE. Land R 130
TR 01511 6/28/2018 EVERLASTING ST. Land R 360
TR 01516 11/9/2018 EVERLASTING CIRCLE Land R 360
TR 01545 5/25/2018 WINTERGREEN ST. Land R 300
TR 01546 6/14/2018 WINTERGREEN ST. Land R 300
TR 01555 3/2/2018 WINTERGREEN ST. Land R 360
TR 01556 3/2/2018 WINTERGREEN ST. Land R 360

2019

TR 01103 2/12/2019 ROSEMARY ST. Land R 376
TR 01108 7/8/2019 ROSEMARY ST. Land R 240
TR 01120 11/15/2019 QUERCUS COR. YELLOW BELL Land R 396
TR 01145 5/31/2019 ORCHIDS ST. Land R 373
TR 01154 5/7/2019 ORCHIDS ST. Land R 382
TR 01178 7/26/2019 PRIMROSE ST. Land R 240
TR 01195 5/30/2019 QUERCUS ST. Land R 120
TR 01208 11/19/2019 ROSEMARY COR XYLOMELUM Land R 356
TR 01213 1/4/2019 XYLOMELUM ST. Land R 300
TR 01224 1/25/2019 FLEUR DE LIZ ST. Land R 200
TR 01242 10/10/2019 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA ST. Land R 544
TR 01253 12/16/2019 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA EXT. Land R 128
TR 01257 10/30/2019 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA AVE. EXT. Land R 325
TR 01263 11/21/2019 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA ST. Land R 96
TR 01265 10/16/2019 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA ST. Land R 130
TR 01288 9/2/2019 SUNFLOWER ST. Land R 180
TR 01330 6/3/2019 VERBENA ST. Land R 240

TR 01335 4/1/2019 GARDENIA COR. VERBENA Land R 357
TR 01341 4/2/2019 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA Land R 300
TR 01381 7/17/2019 MORNING GLORY ST. Land R 150
TR 01388 5/30/2019 S. ALVENDIA AVE COR NARCISSUS ST. Land R 211
TR 01392 5/30/2019 NARCISSUS ST. Land R 150
TR 01393 7/24/2019 NARCISSUS ST. Land R 150
TR 01394 5/30/2019 NARCISSUS ST. Land R 150
TR 01398 10/14/2019 NARCISSUS ST. Land R 240
TR 01406 10/14/2019 ORCHIDS COR XYLOMELUM ST. Land R 349
TR 01419 12/18/2019 PRIMROSE ST. Land R 240.00
TR 01426 3/4/2019 PRIMROSE ST. Land R 240.00
TR 01437 4/15/2019 QUERCUS ST. Land R 240.00
TR 01445 6/26/2019 ROSEMARY ST. Land R 240.00
TR 01460 6/20/2019 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA COR. MORNING GLORY Land R 359
TR 01478 6/20/2019 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA ST. Land R 300
TR 01483 10/25/2019 EVERLASTING CRICLE Land R 300
TR 01486 11/7/2019 EVERLASTING CIRCLE Land R 103
TR 01507 6/25/2019 EVERLASTING CIRCLE Land R 300
TR 01526 10/28/2019 EVERLASTING CIRCLE Land R 359
TR 01527 12/12/2019 EVERLASTING CIRCLE Land R 359
TR 01537 12/6/2019 EVERLASTING CIRCLE Land R 549

2020

TR 01099 12/3/2020 ZINNIA ST. Land R 317
TR 01110 1/30/2020 ROSEMARIE ST. Land R 396
TR 01212 1/15/2020 XYLOMELUM ST. Land R 300
TR 01223 11/16/2020 FLEURDELIZ ST. Land R 141
TR 01142 9/9/2020 PRIMROSE ST. Land R 356
TR 01143 9/9/2020 PRIMROSE ST. Land R 352
TR 01196 7/16/2020 ROSE MARY ST. Land R 240
TR 01201 11/19/2020 ROSEMARY ST. Land R 100
TR 01266 7/30/2020 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA AVE. Land R 190
TR 01334 11/4/2020 VERBENA ST. Land R 240
TR 01246 2/13/2020 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA EXT. Land R 96
TR 01249 2/13/2020 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA AVE. Land R 114
TR 01254 1/23/2020 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA AVE. Land R 688
TR 01264 6/8/2020 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA ST. Land R 100
TR 01336 11/4/2020 HYACINTH COR SOLIVEN Land R 447
TR 01402 3/12/2020 NARCISSUS ST. Land R 140
TR 01430 1/6/2020 QUERCUS ST. Land R 240
TR 01443 2/12/2020 ROSEMARY ST. Land R 240

2021

TR 01094 7/13/2021 ZINNIA ST. Land R 360
TR 01096 7/5/2021 ZINNIA ST. Land R 240
TR 01111 7/19/2021 ROSEMARY ST. Land R 120
TR 01112 7/19/2021 ROSEMARY ST. Land R 120
TR 01113 7/14/2021 ROSEMARY ST. Land R 240
TR 01130 7/30/2021 PRIMROSE ST. Land R 240
TR 01150 7/13/2021 ORCHIDS ST. Land R 162

TR 01151 7/13/2021 ORCHIDS ST. Land R 162
 TR 01162 4/26/2021 MORNING GLORY COR. XYLOMELUM Land R 367
 TR 01202 6/8/2021 ROSEMARY ST. Land R 140
 TR 01236 6/11/2021 SUNFLOWER ST. Land R 73
 TR 01244 1/20/2021 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA EXT. Land R 69
 TR 01245 5/4/2021 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA EXT. Land R 59
 TR 01247 6/14/2021 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA EXT. Land R 65
 TR 01248 1/15/2021 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA AVE. Land R 64
 TR 01276 1/20/2021 EVERLASTING CIRCLE Land R 77
 TR 01282 1/4/2021 FLEUR DE LIZ ST. Land R 322
 TR 01291 3/2/2021 FLEUR DE LIZ Land R 279
 TR 01382 2/2/2021 NARCISSUS COR XYLOMELUM Land R 390
 TR 01428 7/27/2021 QUERCUS ST. Land R 240
 TR 01466 4/26/2021 EVERLASTING ST. Land R 300
 TR 01490 4/21/2021 SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS Land R 360
 TR 01491 4/21/2021 SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS Land R 360
 TR 01492 4/21/2021 SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS Land R 360
 TR 01493 4/21/2021 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA ST. Land R 360
 TR 01494 4/21/2021 SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS Land R 340
 TR 01495 4/21/2021 SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS Land R 366
 TR 01496 4/21/2021 SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS Land R 366
 TR 01497 4/21/2021 SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS Land R 590
 TR 01498 4/21/2021 SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS Land R 1,310
 TR 01541 2/2/2021 WINTERGREEN COR MORNING GLORY Land R 371
 TR 01558 4/26/2021 WINTERGREEN ST. Land R 360

3. LAKEVIEW (Control)

SEQUENCE # DEC. DATE LOCATION KIND CLASSIF. AREA

2009

TR 01988 8/25/2009 LAKEVIEW HOMES I Land R 246 sq. m.
 TR 01990 10/27/2009 ROSAL ST. Land R 121
 TR 02017 1/22/2009 ISABEL ST. SUBD I Land R 200
 TR 02018 1/22/2009 ISABEL ST. SUBD I Land R 200
 TR 02047 6/16/2009 MANGGA ST. Land R 135
 TR 02184 5/27/2009 LAKEVIEW Land R 41.75
 TR 02220 7/21/2009 LAKEVIEW Land R 60
 TR 02295 10/12/2009 LAKEVIEW Land R 248

2010

TR 02071 12/16/2010 LAKEVIEW Land R 63
 TR 02042 2/25/2010 LAKEVIEW Land R 43
 TR 02061 3/18/2010 MANGGA ST. Land R 153
 TR 02174 4/16/2010 SAMPAGUITA ST. Land R 130
 TR 02188 1/20/2010 SAMPAGUITA ST. I Land R 40.93
 TR 02218 7/29/2010 NEAR ESTANISLAO ST. I Land R 700
 TR 02219 11/17/2010 ESPELETA ST. Land R 60
 TR 02300 4/22/2010 LAKEVIEW Land R 248

TR 02308 4/6/2010 LAKEVIEW Land R 251
TR 02310 2/18/2010 CARNATION ST. Land R 373
TR 01986 10/4/2010 LAKEVIEW HOMES I TOPHILL Land R 218
TR 01987 10/4/2010 LAKEVIEW HOMES I TOP HILL Land R 224

2011

TR 02014 10/18/2011 ISABEL ST. Land R 198
TR 02112 3/24/2011 ESTANISLAO ST. Land R 218
TR 02160 3/8/2011 LAKEVIEW Land R 148
TR 02257 3/10/2011 LAKEVIEW Land R 468
TR 02068 2/7/2011 NARRA ST. Land R 126
TR 02070 2/1/2011 LAKEVIEW Land R 126

2012

TR 02035 4/11/2012 NEAR LAKEVIEW Land R 229
TR 02038 5/28/2012 LAKEVIEW Land R 200
TR 02134 4/20/2012 ISABEL ST. Land R 78
TR 02135 4/20/2012 ISABEL ST. Land R 230
TR 02185 8/17/2012 INT. SAMPAGUITA ST. Land R 41.75

2013

TR 02002 11/12/2013 ISABEL ST. Land R 204
TR 02008 12/13/2013 ISABEL ST. Land R 102
TR 02046 7/3/2013 LAKEVIEW Land R 250
TR 02058 11/20/2013 NARRA ST. Land R 224
TR 02069 1/11/2013 NARRA ST. Land R 126
TR 02136 9/13/2013 MARGARITA ST. Land R 180
TR 02196 10/17/2013 INT. SAMPAGUITA ST. Land R 204
TR 02197 10/17/2013 LAKEVIEW Land R 204
TR 02198 10/17/2013 LAKEVIEW Land R 204
TR 02251 1/29/2013 LAKEVIEW Land R 298

2014

TR 02005 3/7/2014 ISABEL ST. Land R 181
TR 02081 5/15/2014 ESTANISLAO ST. Land R 500
TR 02121 12/22/2014 ESTANISLAO ST. Land R 1,353
TR 02124 2/7/2014 ISABEL ST. Land R 300
TR 02155 12/22/2014 ESTANISLAO COR. ROSAL Land R 447
TR 02274 1/22/2014 CATTLEYA ST. Land R 250
TR 02179 3/14/2014 SAMPAGUITA ST. Land R 212
TR 02307 9/30/2014 LAKEVIEW Land R 376
TR 02288 7/23/2014 CARNATION ST. Land R 244
TR 02291 8/27/2014 CATTLEYA COR. CARNATION Land R 107
TR 02309 12/14/2017 605 CARNATION ST. Land R 251

2015

TR 02009 10/8/2015 ISABEL ST. Land R 232
TR 02032 8/11/2015 LAKEVIEW Land R 160
TR 02186 3/9/2015 INT. SAMPAGUITA ST. Land R 41.75
TR 02222 7/2/2015 SAMPAGUITA ST. Land R 100.50

TR 02226 12/17/2015 SAMPAGUITA ST. EXTENSION Land R 568
TR 02267 4/21/2015 LAKEVIEW Land R 210
TR 02290 6/26/2015 CARNATION ST. Land R 252

2016

TR 02158 12/7/2016 ROSAL ST. Land R 383
TR 02159 12/6/2016 MARGARITA ST. Land R 120
TR 02178 3/16/2016 SAMPAGUITA ST. Land R 212
TR 02189 11/24/2016 SAMPAGUITA ST. Land R 583
TR 02225 4/12/2016 SAMPAGUITA ST. EXT. Land R 557
TR 02229 8/17/2016 ESTANISLAO ST. Land R 51
TR 02242 8/17/2016 GENARO COR. ESTANISLAO STS. Land R 121
TR 02243 8/17/2016 ESTANISLAO ST. Land R 121
TR 02244 8/17/2016 ESTANISLAO ST. Land R 106
TR 02252 12/20/2016 MAGNOLIA ST. Land R 298
TR 02275 10/28/2016 CATTLEYA ST. Land R 250
TR 02304 6/10/2016 LAKEVIEW Land R 220

2017

TR 02029 8/8/2017 ISABEL ST. Land R 200
TR 02030 8/8/2017 ISABEL ST. Land R 200
TR 02031 8/8/2017 ISABEL ST. Land R 286
TR 02077 5/4/2017 NARRA ST. Land R 1,580
TR 02084 8/31/2017 LAKEVIEW Land R 106
TR 02109 2/20/2017 ISABEL ST. Land R 220
TR 02171 3/30/2017 SAMPAGUITA ST. Land R 500
TR 02175 5/2/2017 SAMPAGUITA ST. Land R 424
TR 02187 1/9/2017 INT SAMPAGUITA ST. Land R 41.75
TR 02221 5/31/2017 ESPELETA ST. Land R 63
TR 02262 5/26/2017 MAGNOLIA ST. Land R 58
TR 02289 8/23/2017 PRIMROSE ST. Land R 219

2018

TR 02078 1/29/2018 ESTANISLAO ST. Land R 31600
TR 02079 1/29/2018 ESTANISLAO ST. Land R 312
TR 02080 1/29/2018 ESTANISLAO ST. Land R 308
TR 02154 1/19/2018 ROSAL ST. Land R 200
TR 02157 9/26/2018 ROSAL ST. Land R 204
TR 02234 11/26/2018 JULIANA ST. Land R 307
TR 02235 1/30/2018 ESTANISLAO ST. Land R 1,000
TR 02236 1/30/2018 ESTANISLAO ST. Land R 543
TR 02284 3/8/2018 PRIMROSE ST. Land R 136

2019

TR 01995 4/17/2019 ROSAL ST. Land R 216
TR 02043 10/14/2019 226 MANGGA ST. Land R 263
TR 02287 7/2/2019 CARNATION ST. Land R 235
TR 02292 6/14/2019 ASTER ST. Land R 60.50
TR 02313 8/1/2019 CARNATION ST. Land R 299

2020

TR 02041 2/20/2020 MANGGA ST. Land R 400
TR 02151 1/9/2020 ROSAL ST. Land R 200
TR 02156 10/12/2020 MARGARITA ST. Land R 160
TR 02237 8/6/2020 GENARO ST. Land R 192

2021

TR 01989 7/23/2021 MARGARITA ST. Land R 2,825
TR 02205 3/25/2021 SAMPAGUITA ST. Land R 204
TR 02314 3/5/2021 CARNATION ST. Land R 502
TR 02680 6/8/2021 ESTANISLAO ST. Land R 234

APPENDIX D

Sampling Rounds in Pleasant, Greenheights and Lakeview

A. First Round

1. PLEASANT

2010		OUTCOME			
SEQUENCE#	DEC. DATE STREET AREA	TRANSACTION	DATE	AREA	PRICE
TR 02883	5/24 /2010 PENINSULA 300 sq. m.	DOAS	2/8/2010	300	P750, 000
TR 02887	12/23/2010 PENINSULA COR HYATT 358	DOAS	4/15/2010	358	930, 800
TR 02890	8/31/2010 300.00	DOAS	8/6/2010	300	1, 340, 000
TR 02911	12/10/2010 INTERCON 300	DOAS	6/21/2010	300	1, 450, 000
TR 02930	8/18/2010 299	Not found			
(TR 02885 not on initial sample but included by Data Officer)		DOAS	2/15/2010	150	375, 000
(TR 02888 not on initial sample)		DOAS	3/5/2010	300	750, 000

2016		OUTCOME			
TR 01652	9/1/2016 MANDARIN 313	DOAS	7/21/2016	313	10, 956, 000
TR 01655	9/1/2016 MANDARIN 300	DOAS	7/21/2016	300	10, 956, 000
TR 01737	7/4/2016 REGENT 300				
TR 01899	10/27/2016 MANDARIN 275	DOAS	6/14/2016	2, 206	15M (6 lots)
TR 01900	10/27/2016 MANDARIN 287	DOAS	6/14/2016	2, 206	15M (6 lots)
(TR 01729- not on 2016 list as it was in 2017)		DOAS	12/7/2016	300	3, 600, 000

2019		OUTCOME			
TR 01687	9/2/2019 PENINSULA 336	DOAS	5/16/2019	336	4, 289, 362
TR 01697	12/5/2019 PENINSULA 309	<i>Dacion</i>	3/11/2019		
TR 01713	10/14/2019 REGENT 300	Donation	7/8/2019		
TR 01751	4/24/2019 PENINSULA 321	DOAS	3/4/2019	321	3, 500, 000
TR 01754	9/30/2019 PENINSULA 305	Not found			

2. SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS

2010		OUTCOME			
SEQUENCE#	DEC. DATE STREET AREA	TRANSACTION	DATE	AREA	PRICE
TR 02703	1/29/2010 ZINNIA ST 240 sq. m.	Not found			
TR 02722	1/20/2010 ORCHIDS 292	DOAS	8/24/2009	292	P550, 000
TR 02819	2/2/2011 300	Not found			
TR 02839	8/31/2010 WINTERGREEN 300	DOAS	8/24/2010	300	620, 000
TR 02847	8/2/2010 WINTERGREEN 370	DOAS	7/28/2010	370	1, 200, 000

2016		OUTCOME			
TR 01157	1/18/2016 ORCHIDS 312	DOAS but 9/1/2015			
TR 01190	8/23/2016 QUERCUS 240				
TR 01231	6/30/2016 SUNFLOWER 300	DOAS but 11/26/2015			
TR 01307	7/19/2016 VERBENA 240				
TR 01474	5/24/2016 S. ALVENDIA 300	Extrajudicial settlement (EJS) 3/17/2015			

2019		OUTCOME			
TR 01154	5/7/2019 ORCHIDS 382	DOAS	5/7/2019	382	P2, 500, 000

TR 01178 7/26/2019 PRIMROSE 240			
TR 01242 10/10/2019 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA 544			
TR 01265 10/16/2019 SOLIVEN ALVENDIA 130	DOAS	10/3/2019	130 4, 300, 000
TR 01388 5/30/2019 S. ALVENDIA COR NARCISSUS 211	DOAS	2/7/2019	211 2, 110, 000
(TR 01490 <i>not on initial sample but included by Data Officer</i>)	DOAS	12/7/2019	360 68.124M
			(total area: 7, 580 sq. m.)
(TR 01493 not on initial list)	DOAS	12/17/2019	360 68.124M
			(total area: 7, 580 sq. m.)

3. LAKEVIEW I (Control Group)

2010	OUTCOME		
SEQUENCE# DEC. DATE STREET AREA	TRANSACTION DATE	AREA	PRICE
TR 02174 4/16/2010 SAMPAGUITA 130	DOAS	3/23/2010	130 P100, 000
TR 02188 1/20/2010 SAMPAGUITA 40.93	DOAS	8/24/2009	40.93 35, 000
TR 02218 7/29/2010 NEAR ESTANISLAO 700	Correction of information		
TR 02308 4/6/2010 251	No attachment		
TR 02310 2/18/2010 CARNATION 373	Blank		

2016	OUTCOME		
TR 02178 3/16/2016 SAMPAGUITA 212	No attachment		
TR 02189 11/24/2016 SAMPAGUITA 583	EJS No date		
TR 02225 4/12/2016 SAMPAGUITA EXT. 557	DOAS	12/4/2015	557 1, 114, 000
TR 02243 8/17/2016 ESTANISLAO 121	No attachment (no date)		
TR 02252 12/20/2016 MAGNOLIA 298	DOAS	6/4/2014	298 1, 000, 000

2019	OUTCOME		
TR 01995 4/17/2019 ROSAL 216	Not found		
TR 02043 10/14/2019 MANGGA 263	Not found		
TR 02287 7/2/2019 CARNATION 235	EJS	3/ 13/ 2019	
TR 02292 6/14/2019 ASTER 60.50	DOAS	2/27/2019	60. 50 650, 000
TR 02313 8/1/2019 CARNATION 299	DOAS	7/8/2019	299 1, 800, 00

B. Second Round

1. PLEASANT

2010	OUTCOME		
SEQUENCE# DEC. DATE STREET AREA	TRANSACTION DATE	AREA	PRICE
TR 02930 8/18/2010 _____ 299 sq. m.	Not found		
2011			
TR 02885 3/17/2011 Peninsula 150	DOAS	2/15/2010	150 P375, 000
2016			
TR 01735 7/11/2016 Regent 333	DOAS	4/10/2014	333 832, 500
TR 01736 7/11/2016 Regent 202	DOAS	4/10/2014	202 505, 000
TR 01654 9/1/2016 Mandarin 300	No attachment		
TR 01660 10/13/2016 Mandarin 300	DOAS	10/2016	300 3, 600, 000
TR 01898 10/27/2016 Mandarin 270	DOAS	10/14/2016	270 among 6 lots
			<i>totaling 2, 206 sq. m. sold for P15M</i>
TR 01901 10/27/2016 Mandarin 344	DOAS	10/14/2016	344 among 6 lots
			<i>totaling 2, 206 sq.m. sold for P15M</i>
TR 01902 10/27/2016 Mandarin 414	DOAS	10/14/2016	414 among 6 lots
			<i>totaling 2, 206 sq.m. sold for P15M</i>
TR 01897 10/20/2016 Mandarin 286	DOAS	9/4/2016	286 3, 500, 000

2017

TR 01885	3/14/2017	Peninsula	300	DOAS	2/1/2017	300	3,600,000
----------	-----------	-----------	-----	------	----------	-----	-----------

2019

TR 01754	9/30/2019	Peninsula	305	DOAS	9/20/2018	305	multiple sales, amount not indicated
TR 01714	10/14/2019	Regent	300	Deed of Donation (DOD)			
TR 01688	9/2/2019	Peninsula	312	DOAS	5/16/2019	312	3,982,979
TR 01696	10/24/2019	Peninsula	300	DOAS	7/5/2019	300	3,600,000
TR 01712	10/14/2019	Regent	300	DOD			
TR 01668	4/15/2019	Hyatt	100	DOAS	8/20/2018	100	1,200,000

2020

TR 01695	9/28/2020	Peninsula	300	DOAS	1/19/1989	300	30,000
TR 01700	12/3/2020	Hyatt	330	DOAS	9/19/1991	330	100,000
TR 01752	9/28/2020	Peninsula	306	DOAS	5/22/1989	306	30,000
TR 01796	10/26/2020	Mandarin	300	EJS	4/23/2018	300	

2. SOUTH GREENHEIGHTS**2010**

SEQUENCE #	DEC. DATE	STREET AREA	TRANSACTION	OUTCOME DATE	AREA	PRICE
TR 02728	12/22/2010	QUERCUS 240		Not found		
TR 02838	12/29/2010	300	DOAS	11/30/2010	300	P750,000
TR 02830	11/26/2010	359		No attachment		
TR 02848	11/12/2010	WINTERGREEN 360		EJS		
TR 02849	8/2/2010	WINTERGREEN 180		No attachment		
TR 02725	7/16/2010	PRIMROSE 276		No attachment		

2011

TR 02814	1/10/2011	EVERLASTING 300	DOAS	1/19/2011	300	630,000
TR 02811	1/31/2011	S. ALVENDIA 300	DOAS	1/18/2010	300	700,000
TR 02746	2/10/2011	S. ALVENDIA 194	DOAS	1/19/2011	194	400,000

2016

TR 01167	12/2/2016	PRIMROSE 258				
TR 01553	10/5/2016	WINTERGREEN 360	DOAS	7/22/2016	300	1,260,000
TR 01275	10/20/2016	EVERLASTING 73	DOAS	9/6/2016	73	474,000
TR 01314	9/23/2016	HYACINTH 270	DOAS	8/9/2016	270	1,080,000
TR 01353	9/9/2016	S. ALVENDIA-JASMINE 321	DOAS	4/22/2016	321	1,500,000
TR 01205	9/1/2016	YELLOW BELL 165	DOAS	7/20/2016	165	1,072,000

2017

TR 01165	1/11/2017	PRIMROSE 291	DOAS	12/8/2016	291	1,300,000
TR 01532	1/23/2017	S. ALVENDIA 396	DOAS	2/9/2016	396	1,500,000
TR 01109	2/16/2017	ROSEMARY 240	DOAS	1/10/2017	240	800,000

2019

TR 01419	12/18/2019	PRIMROSE 240	DOAS	3/6/2019	240	1,920,000
TR 01253	12/16/2019	S. ALVENDIA EXT. 128	DOAS	10/30/2019	128	1,536,000
TR 01527	12/12/2019	EVERLASTING 359				
TR 01537	12/6/2019	EVERLASTING 549				
TR 01263	11/21/2019	SOLIVEN ALVENDIA 96	DOAS	10/30/2019	96	1,152,000

2020

TR 01212	1/15/2020	XYLOMELUM 300	DOAS	No date	300	45,000
TR 01110	1/30/2020	ROSEMARIE 396	DOAS	12/13/2019	396	2,376,000
TR 01430	1/6/2020	QUERCUS 240	DOAS	10/18/2019	240	2,107,000

TR 01254 1/23/2020 S. ALVENDIA AV. 688 DOAS 12/11/2019 688 2, 000, 000

3. LAKEVIEW

				OUTCOME			
2010	SEQUENCE #	DEC. DATE	STREET AREA	TRANSACTION	DATE	AREA	PRICE
	TR 02071	12/16/2010	--- 63 sq m	DOAS	1/18/2010	63	120, 000
	TR 02219	11/17/2010	Espeleta 60	Not found as it was mistyped 02019			
	TR 01986	10/04/2010	Tophill 1 218	No attachment			
	TR 02300	4/22/2010	--- 248	DOAS	3/18/2010	248	400, 000
2011							
	TR 02160	3/08/2011	__ 148	DOAS	2/4/2011	148	312, 000
	TR 02068	2/07/2011	Narra 126	DOAS	8/9/2010	126	200, 000
	TR 02070	2/01/2011	__ 126	DOAS	11/19/2010	126	693, 000
	TR 02112	3/24/2011	Estanislao 218	DOAS	12/23/2010	218	450, 000
2016							
	TR 02242	8/17/2016	Genaro cor. Estanislao 121	DOAS	5/20/2016	121	1, 620, 000
	TR 02159	12/06/2016	Margarita 120	No attachment			
	TR 02244	8/17/2016	Estanislao 106	No attachment			
	TR 02275	10/28/2016	Cattleya 250	DOAS	1/29/2013		
	TR 02158	12/7/2016	Rosal 383	EJS			
2017							
	TR 02109	2/20/2017	Isabel 220	Affidavit of self-adjudication			
	TR 02187	1/9/2017	Int. Sampaguita 41.75	Deed of Donation			
	TR 02262	5/26/2017	Magnolia 58	DOAS	12/15/2016	58	368, 000
	TR 02221	5/31/2017	Espeleta 63	Deed of Donation			
2019							
	TR 01995	4/17/2019	Rosal 216.00	Correction of name			
	TR 02043	10/14/2019	Mangga 263.00	Correction			
2020							
	TR 02041	2/20/2020	Mangga 400	DOAS	6/3/2019		
	TR 02151	1/9/2020	Rosal 200	EJS			
	TR 02237	8/6/2020	Genaro 192	EJS			

C. Third Round

1. LAKEVIEW

				OUTCOME			
2016	SEQUENCE #	DEC. DATE	STREET AREA	TRANSACTION	DATE	AREA	PRICE
	TR 02304,	6/10/2016,	220 sq m.	DOAS	3/15/2016	220	850, 000
	TR 02229,	8/17/2016	51 sq. m.	DOAS	5/12/2016	31	382, 500
2017							
	TR 02175	5/2/2017,	424 q. m.	DOAS	3/16/2017	424	2, 756, 000
	TR 02077,	5/4/2017,	1, 580 sq. m.	DOAS	3/24/2016	1,580	12, 700, 000

2. PLEASANT

For Verification

2016

TR 01655, 7/21/2016, Mandarin, 300 sq.m. (sold for P36, 520/sq. m. for a total of P10.956 million), or more than 3x the zonal value of P12,000/sq. m. at the time).

TR 01652, 7/21/2016, Mandarin, 313 sq.m. (also for P10.956 million).

OUTCOME:

TR 01652 DOAS 7/21/2016, Mandarin, 313 sq.m. (3 lots sold for P10.956 million with total area of 913 sq. m.